

worm

**Waste in humanitarian Operations:
Reduction and Minimisation**

D6.2. Policy framework supporting waste picker's livelihoods (policy brief)

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	FULL NAME
ACF	Action Against Hunger
BHA	Bureau for Humanitarian Assistance
BBC	buy-back centres
CRS	Catholic Relief Services
DFID	Department for International Development
DRC	Danish Refugee Council
EC	European Commission
EPR	Extended Producer Responsibility
FRC	Finnish Red Cross
IAWP	International Alliance of Waste Pickers
ICRC	International Committee of the Red Cross
IMC	International Medical Corps
IOM	International Organization for Migration
MBO	Membership-based organization
MRF	Material Recovery Facility
NCA	Norwegian Church Aid
NGO	Non-governmental organization
PPE	Personal protective equipment

PPP	Public-private partnership
PSA	Pamela Steele Associates
SLF	Sustainable Livelihoods Framework
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
UN	United Nations
VNRC	Viet Nam Red Cross Society
WORM	Waste in humanitarian Operations: Reduction and Minimization
WPs	Work Packages

TABLE OF CONTENT

LIST OF ACRONYMS	3
LIST OF FIGURES	7
LIST OF TABLES	7
BACKGROUND ABOUT WORM	8
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
NON-TECHNICAL SUMMARY	8
1. INTRODUCTION	9
FIGURE 1 HIERARCHY OF (PLASTIC) RECYCLING (BARFORD & AHMAD, 2021).	11
2. METHOD AND DATA	11
2.1. INPUT FROM END-USERS	11
2.2. EXISTING AND INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS	12
2.3. STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOPS	12
2.4. SITE VISITS IN KENYA AND VIETNAM	12
2.5. INTERVIEWS WITH WASTE PICKERS	13
2.6. GREY AND ACADEMIC LITERATURE	13
3. KEY CHALLENGES AND RISKS	13
3.1. RISKS TO HEALTH AND SAFETY	14
3.2. INCOME INSECURITY AND EXPLOITATION	14
3.3. UNCERTAIN MARKET ACCESS	15
3.4. FEAR OF FORMAL INSTITUTIONS AND LACK OF FORMAL INCLUSION	15
3.5. LIMITED EDUCATION AND TRAINING	15
3.6. CHILD LABOUR/GENERATIONAL WASTE PICKING	16
3.7. GENDER-BASED VULNERABILITIES	16
3.8. SOCIAL CHALLENGES, STIGMA, AND TENSIONS	16
3.9. LACK OF/INADEQUATE INFRASTRUCTURE	17
3.10. ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS AND RISKS	17
4. HUMANITARIAN WASTE PICKING INITIATIVES	17
4.1. EXAMPLES FROM PRACTICE	17
4.2. MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF EXISTING PROJECTS	18
5. SUSTAINABLE LIVELIHOODS FRAMEWORK (SLF)	20
FIGURE 2 SUSTAINABLE LIVELIHOODS FRAMEWORK (SLF). ADAPTED FROM (DFID, 1999).	21
5.1. VULNERABILITY CONTEXT	21
5.2. LIVELIHOOD ASSETS	21
5.3. TRANSFORMING STRUCTURES AND PROCESSES	22
5.4. LIVELIHOOD STRATEGIES	22
5.5. LIVELIHOOD OUTCOMES	23
6. POLICY FRAMEWORK: SUSTAINABLE LIVELIHOODS FOR WASTE PICKERS	23
6.1. GUIDING PRINCIPLES	23
TABLE 1: CHALLENGES FACED BY INFORMAL WASTE PICKERS, LINKED TO GUIDING PRINCIPLES AND CORRESPONDING TYPES OF CAPITAL UNDER THE SLF (DFID, 1999), WITH EXAMPLES.	24
6.2. STEP-BY-STEP IMPLEMENTATION APPROACH	27

FIGURE 3 KEY COMPONENTS FOR SUSTAINABLE LIVELIHOOD PROGRAMME DEVELOPMENT, INCLUDING GUIDING PRINCIPLES, STEP-BY-STEP APPROACH, AND RELEVANT STAKEHOLDERS. 28

6.3. ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES 33

6.4. INTEGRATION WITH LOCAL AND/OR INNOVATIVE WM BUSINESS MODELS
34

FIGURE 4 AMENDED CIRCULAR ECONOMY, MODIFIED WITH A REFERENCE TO WASTE PICKERS (BARFORD & AHMAD, 2021). 36

7. CONCLUSIONS 36

8. REFERENCES 37

ANNEX 1..... 38

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 Hierarchy of (plastic) recycling (Barford & Ahmad, 2021).....	11
Figure 2 Sustainable Liveihoods Framework (SLF). Adapted from (DFID, 1999).	21
Figure 3 Key components for sustainable livelihood programme development including guiding principles, step-by-step approach, and relevant stakeholders.....	28
Figure 4 Amended circular economy, modified with a reference to waste pickers (Barford & Ahmad, 2021).	36

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Challenges faced by informal waste pickers, linked to guiding principles and corresponding types of capital under the SLF (DFID, 1999), with examples.....	24
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BACKGROUND ABOUT WORM

WORM aims to design guidelines and support actions for the circular economy in the humanitarian sector. It integrates bio-based technological solutions, leverages procurement for waste reduction, improves waste management methods, and prioritises the sustainable livelihoods of waste pickers. WORM focuses on two selected settings: field hospital deployments and humanitarian livelihood programmes with a waste-picking component. Following a collaborative and multi-actor approach, WORM brings together medical and humanitarian organizations, procurement service providers, logistics providers, waste management services, and academic partners.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a deliverable of the WORM Project, funded under the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101135392.

This document aims to address the need to integrate informal waste pickers into humanitarian livelihood programmes as a pathway to social inclusion, environmental sustainability, and economic resilience. Waste pickers play a critical role in reducing landfill waste, preventing pollution, and advancing circular economy goals, yet they remain among the most marginalized workers globally—facing significant health hazards, income insecurity, and social stigma.

The report proposes a comprehensive policy framework grounded in the Sustainable Livelihoods Framework (SLF) and informed by field research, stakeholder workshops, and case studies from Kenya, Vietnam, and other contexts. Key principles include dignity, health and safety, formal recognition, economic inclusion, capacity building, and environmental stewardship. The framework emphasizes co-design with waste pickers, integration with local waste management systems, and alignment with circular economy strategies according to a ten-step process including (1) goal and scope; (2) stakeholder identification; (3) data collection; (4) waste value chain mapping; (5) programme design and planning; (6) capacity building, training, and education; (7) infrastructure and equipment provision; (8) formalization and legal advocacy; (9) market engagement and value chain development; and (10) monitoring, evaluation, adaptation, and outreach. Furthermore, we also provide recommendations on how to integrate livelihoods programmes with a waste picking component into existing/innovative circular economy business models.

NON-TECHNICAL SUMMARY

WORMS aims to support the humanitarian sector in developing policy for programmes that promote sustainable livelihoods for informal waste pickers. This document describes the main challenges faced by waste pickers and introduces a policy framework to guide practitioners. This includes guiding principles, a step-by-step approach, roles and responsibilities, as well as recommendations on how to integrate with existing and/or innovative circular economy business models.

1. INTRODUCTION

Globally, informal employment accounts for 58% of the world’s workforce—approximately two billion workers—underscoring its critical role in economic systems (ILO, 2025a). Within this vast informal economy, an estimated 15–20 million individuals earn their livelihoods through the collection and recycling of municipal solid waste, commonly referred to as waste picking (Morais et al., 2022). Waste pickers often operate at the margins of society, collecting, sorting, and processing discarded materials from streets, waterways, and landfills. Their income depends on volatile commodity markets, and they often work without formal recognition, social protection, or occupational safety measures (WIEGO, 2020).

Waste pickers play an essential role in reducing the amount of waste ending up in landfills and open dumpsites (Morais et al., 2022). They recover and recycle valuable materials, such as paper, cardboard, plastics, and scrap metals, and their activities help conserve resources, reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and close resource loops in the circular economy (Shift, 2022). In addition to environmental benefits, waste picking provides a source of income for some of the most vulnerable communities, offering social utility in contexts of poverty, inequality, and limited formal employment opportunities (Schenck, Blaauw, Viljoen, et al., 2019). Factors such as rapid urbanization, climate change, and inadequate governance structures have further increased reliance on informal recycling systems in developing countries (Dias, 2016; Morais et al., 2022).

Despite their contributions, waste pickers remain socially stigmatized and disconnected from formal waste management systems. They face severe occupational hazards, including exposure to contaminated waste, infectious diseases, and injuries during collection. Vulnerable groups—such as women, children, and persons with disabilities—are disproportionately affected, facing heightened risks of exploitation, harassment, and health impacts (Schenck, Blaauw, Viljoen, et al., 2019). Poor waste management practices, such as open burning and uncontrolled dumping, exacerbate these dangers, leading to environmental pollution, blocked drainage systems, flooding, and increased transmission of infections and disease. These conditions not only harm waste workers but also threaten community health, ecosystems, and economic development.

This crisis disproportionately affects countries that frequently receive humanitarian aid, many of which lack adequate infrastructure and management systems to handle regular solid waste, let alone the additional waste generated by humanitarian efforts. In these contexts, waste picking has emerged as a potential livelihood strategy that offers dual benefits: income generation for vulnerable populations and improved local waste management. However, integrating waste picking into humanitarian programmes requires careful planning to ensure safety, dignity, and economic viability. Without robust safeguards, such initiatives risk perpetuating exploitation and health hazards rather than alleviating poverty and promoting resilience.

Formalization of waste picking is often proposed as a solution to improve working conditions, provide legal recognition, and enable fair bargaining mechanisms. While formalization can bring significant benefits, evidence shows that policies vary widely across countries and often fail to deliver these improvements in practice (Morais et al., 2022). Moreover, the role of waste pickers in advancing circular economy goals remains undervalued in development agendas, despite their proven contributions to resource recovery and environmental protection (Gutberlet, 2023).

Deliverable 6.2 (D6.2) responds to this challenge by developing a comprehensive policy framework for sustainable humanitarian livelihood programmes that incorporate waste picking. Led by Kühne Logistics University (KLU) in collaboration with RMIT, Innovasjon Norge, and end-users—including Action Against Hunger (ACF), Catholic Relief Services (CRS), the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC), International Medical Corps (IMC), the Norwegian Refugee Council (NRC), the Pamela Steele Associates (PSA), and the Viet Nam Red Cross Society (VNRC)—the framework emphasizes co-design, empowerment,

and collective action, ensuring that waste pickers are active participants in programme development and implementation. It also prioritizes health, safety, and gender equity, while promoting circular economy principles and economic and environmental sustainability.

D6.2 offers practical guidance for humanitarian actors, policymakers, and development partners. It aims to support the creation of inclusive, rights-based livelihood opportunities that strengthen resilience, uphold human dignity, and contribute to sustainable waste management systems. By recognizing and (voluntarily) formalizing the role of waste pickers, these programmes can transform a marginalized activity into a pathway for sustainable livelihoods.

In the next section, we outline the informal waste sector and its hierarchy, showing where waste pickers fit within the recycling value chain. The remainder of this document is structured as follows: first, we present the methodology and data collection steps; next, we examine the challenges faced by informal waste pickers and highlight existing humanitarian and circular economy initiatives. We then introduce the Sustainable Livelihoods Framework (SLF) developed by DFID (1999), followed by an overview of the proposed policy framework for sustainable humanitarian livelihood programmes with a waste-picking component. This includes guiding principles, a step-by-step implementation approach, roles and responsibilities, and integration with existing business models. Finally, we conclude with key findings and next steps.

Who are waste pickers and how are they organized?

Waste pickers¹ are individuals who earn a living by recovering, sorting, and selling recyclable materials from municipal solid waste streams—often collected from streets, waterways, dumpsites, and landfills (Morais et al., 2022). While their contribution to waste management and the circular economy is undeniable, their activities and working conditions vary widely across contexts, making generalization difficult.

Waste picking exists along a broad spectrum of formalization. At one end, unorganized individuals are working in highly precarious conditions, sometimes under exploitative arrangements or even controlled by criminal networks. At the other end, well-structured cooperatives operate like professional enterprises—paying taxes, offering social security benefits, and providing safer working environments. These variations blur the line between what is considered “informal” and “formal” (Velis, 2017).

Generally, waste pickers fall into three main categories (Buch et al., 2021):

- **Unorganized (independent):** Individuals working alone or in small groups, collecting low-value recyclables from streets and dumpsites.
- **Organized:** Waste pickers affiliated with cooperatives, unions, or membership-based organizations that provide better bargaining power and sometimes social protections.
- **Contract labourers:** Workers hired by intermediaries or companies for specific waste collection tasks.

Figure 1 illustrates the hierarchy of plastic recycling, though it can also serve to visualize the general structure of other material flows within the informal waste sector (Barford & Ahmad, 2021). While this structure varies by local context, economic value tends to increase as materials move upward along the informal waste management value chain (HELP Logistics, 2024):

¹Note that terminology may vary based on countries and regions, however, in this deliverable the term, “waste picker” refers to individuals who pick/collect waste to earn livelihoods. This may be from landfills, streets, etc., but can also be those who collect informally from households.

- **Base level (waste pickers):** Waste-picking communities (unorganized and organized) collect low-value recyclables under conditions of social and economic vulnerability, selling to waste collectors and middle agents.
- **Level two (waste collectors):** Waste collectors and scrap dealers handle higher-value materials such as metals and e-waste, selling them to middle agents.
- **Level three (middle agents):** Middle agents supply recycling facilities, where materials are cleaned, processed, and reintroduced into production or export markets.

Figure 1 Hierarchy of (plastic) recycling (Barford & Ahmad, 2021).

This hierarchy reflects deep social and economic disparities. While waste pickers provide essential environmental services—reducing landfill waste, preventing pollution, and supporting circular economy goals—they remain among the most marginalized workers globally, facing health risks, social stigma, and unstable incomes. Despite these challenges, waste pickers are increasingly aware of their contribution to sustainability and are organizing to demand recognition and rights (Dias, 2016).

2. METHOD AND DATA

The development of the policy framework under D6.2 followed a multi-method approach to ensure relevance, inclusiveness, and practical applicability. The methodology was primarily qualitative, combining data from existing programmes or projects with a waste-picking component, evidence from established and innovative local waste management business models, and primary data collected through site visits, stakeholder workshops, and interviews with waste pickers. The research was then complemented with findings from the academic and grey literature.

2.1. INPUT FROM END-USERS

Firstly, end-users provided us information and documentation on their existing programmes or projects with a waste-picking component. This included documents such as project reports or presentation slides.

Additionally, we conducted follow up interviews to ask specific questions about the projects. None of the end-users had formal programmes; rather, they were engaged through specific projects or initiatives. Among these organizations, ACF, CRS, NRC, PSA, and VNRC were actively involved or had previously participated in relevant projects. We then analysed the data provided to extract insights on identified challenges, activities, outcomes, and future recommendations to support the development of this policy brief.

2.2. EXISTING AND INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS

Findings from Task 3.1, led by RMIT, were used to contextualize humanitarian programmes within the landscape of existing and innovative local WM business models. This approach ensured that the proposed policy framework aligns with local economic structures and environmental goals, enhancing feasibility and sustainability. Innovasjon Norge contributed technical expertise on innovative business models and circular economy principles, which helped shape the framework’s attention to new and innovative ideas to promote sustainable livelihoods for informal waste pickers.

2.3. STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOPS

Two workshops—one in Kenya and one in Vietnam, each with approximately 15–20 participants—were organized with external stakeholders, including local authorities, private sector representatives, humanitarian actors, and waste picker representatives. These sessions facilitated a dialogue and were a first step to ensure the framework considers diverse perspectives and local needs. Participants were divided into three groups, with each group tasked to identify environmental, social, or economic challenges and opportunities associated with informal waste picking and the informal waste sector, guided by the following questions:

- What are the potential **social challenges** (e.g., health and safety) for waste pickers?
- What are the potential **social opportunities** (e.g., working as part of a community) for waste pickers?
- What are the potential **economic challenges** (e.g., high uncertainty) for waste pickers?
- What are the potential **economic opportunities** (e.g., reselling materials) for waste pickers?
- What are the potential **environmental challenges** (e.g., uncontrolled waste) for waste pickers?
- What are the potential **environmental opportunities** (e.g., recycling) for waste pickers?

Drawing on responses from workshop participants, as well as insights from interviews and discussions with waste pickers, we compiled a list of challenges related to achieving sustainable livelihoods for waste pickers. Additionally, the identified “opportunities” served as key inputs for developing guidelines and steps to support sustainable livelihood programmes described in the later sections.

2.4. SITE VISITS IN KENYA AND VIETNAM

Another key component of data collection for this deliverable was conducting site visits in Kenya and Vietnam with local waste management experts, organizations, government representatives, and, perhaps most importantly, waste pickers themselves². We carried out two site visits in Kenya and three in Vietnam. In Kenya, visits focused on two local companies working with the informal waste sector. In Vietnam, we

² Due to the sensitive nature of these projects and the organizations’ request, we keep them anonymous. Those who have been quoted below have given their permission, although they remain anonymous.

visited two government agencies and one research organization involved in projects supporting local informal waste pickers.

Although this deliverable aims to be generalizable across multiple contexts, these local site visits were essential for gaining insights into how projects that promote sustainable livelihoods for waste pickers are developed and implemented in different settings. These findings were then combined with other data sources to identify common patterns and develop a strategy suitable for broader application. The visits also included selected programme sites to observe operations, engage with beneficiaries, and assess the practical realities of informal waste picking. This ground-level perspective provided critical validation for the policy recommendations.

2.5. INTERVIEWS WITH WASTE PICKERS

As the final step in primary data collection, WORM prioritized hearing directly from informal waste pickers. We conducted interviews with two individuals—one from Vietnam and one from Kenya—to understand their specific challenges and expectations for a policy framework that supports sustainable livelihoods. Both respondents have extensive experience in waste picking and serve as influential voices within their communities.

The participant from Vietnam, a Vietnam War veteran, has worked in the informal waste sector for over thirteen years. He is a leader within the waste-picking community and collaborates with other members of the local Veterans' Association. The Kenyan participant began collecting waste at the age of ten and has nearly twenty years of experience. He now leads as CEO and founder of Dandora Green Recyclers, an initiative focused on creating sustainable livelihoods through recycling, raising community awareness, building market opportunities, reducing plastic pollution, generating employment, and advancing the circular economy.

2.6. GREY AND ACADEMIC LITERATURE

Finally, we complemented our primary data collection with insights from both academic and grey literature. High-quality research on waste pickers has been conducted globally, much of it published in prestigious journals in the fields of waste management, environmental science, and urban development, as well as by reputable publishers and professional associations (Morais et al., 2022). Over the past few decades, waste pickers have increasingly attracted scholarly attention across diverse academic disciplines, resulting in a significant growth of literature on the topic (Dias, 2016).

While these sources were not the primary contributors to our deliverable, they played an important role in ensuring that no critical elements were overlooked in developing the framework. Our primary data collection focused mainly on the Kenyan and Vietnamese contexts, supplemented by insights from projects supporting sustainable livelihoods for informal waste pickers led by humanitarian organizations and end-users. To ensure broader applicability, we incorporated additional sources to validate and generalize our findings beyond the two country contexts.

3. KEY CHALLENGES AND RISKS

Despite their vital contribution to environmental protection and public health, informal waste pickers often operate under conditions that expose them to significant risks. This section highlights the most common challenges reported by waste picker representatives and examines the factors that exacerbate these vulnerabilities. They are based on both primary (e.g., interviews, site visits, and workshops) and secondary (e.g., academic studies) sources. While the severity and nature of these issues vary across contexts, evidence shows that human rights violations in this sector are frequently serious, systemic, and widespread (Morais et al., 2022; Schenck, Blaauw, Viljoen, et al., 2019; Shift, 2022).

3.1. RISKS TO HEALTH AND SAFETY

Informal waste pickers face significant health and safety risks due to constant exposure to hazardous materials, chemicals, toxic fumes, and biological or medical waste (Kain et al., 2022; Morais et al., 2022; Schenck, Blaauw, Viljoen, et al., 2019; Shift, 2022). The absence of personal protective equipment (PPE) greatly increases the likelihood of injuries and infections (Barford & Ahmad, 2021; Morais et al., 2022; Schenck, Blaauw, Viljoen, et al., 2019; Shift, 2022; Uhunamure et al., 2021). Navigating unstable landfills without proper safety gear increases the likelihood of injuries from collapses, sharp objects, and falls (Schenck, Blaauw, Viljoen, et al., 2019). Toxic fumes from burning plastics, dust, and chemical particles contribute to respiratory illnesses, while extreme heat and lack of shade lead to dehydration and heatstroke (Schenck, Blaauw, Viljoen, et al., 2019; Uhunamure et al., 2021).

“I have access to PPE though most of the waste pickers we work with don’t have such safety gear.”

- *Informal waste picker, Kenya*

- *Informal waste picker, Vietnam*

Beyond the landfill, living conditions further compound these risks. Many waste pickers reside in crowded areas with limited access to clean water and sanitation (Barford & Ahmad, 2021; Paul et al., 2012; Schenck, Blaauw, Viljoen, et al., 2019). Homes located near dumpsites are vulnerable to soil and water contamination, bringing pollutants indoors. Waste sites also serve as breeding grounds for disease-carrying insects and rodents, increasing exposure to illnesses transmitted by mosquitoes, cockroaches, flies, and rats (Morais et al., 2022; Schenck, Blaauw, Viljoen, et al., 2019). Out of necessity, some waste pickers collect food from landfills, which poses additional risks of contamination and illness (Schenck, Blaauw, Viljoen, et al., 2019). The lack of health insurance and protective equipment amplifies these vulnerabilities, leaving waste pickers highly exposed to both occupational and environmental hazards.

3.2. INCOME INSECURITY AND EXPLOITATION

Waste pickers typically live in situations of extreme poverty, and economic insecurity and exploitation remain persistent challenges (Kain et al., 2022; Morais et al., 2022; Shift, 2022). The informal nature of waste picking means earnings are highly unstable, fluctuating with volatile market prices, a lack of transparency, an absence of fixed contracts, dependence on intermediaries, and limited bargaining power (Fair Circularity Initiative, 2024; Paul et al., 2012; Shift, 2022).

Although waste pickers are paid for the materials they collect, they receive no compensation for their labour or the public service they provide (Shift, 2022). This financial vulnerability often traps workers in cycles of debt, forcing many to rely on loan sharks (Kain et al., 2022) and the lack of capital to invest in better equipment or scale up operations limits growth potential (Fair Circularity Initiative, 2024). Health-related expenses further strain household budgets, as most waste pickers cannot afford medical insurance or treatment in case it is not provided by social services. Injuries not only reduce disposable income but also limit the ability to work, reinforcing a vicious cycle of poverty that restricts access to livelihood opportunities (Morais et al., 2022).

“Waste pickers often eat food that comes from waste. It is not something we are happy about, but it is something that is happening on the ground. It is happening because we do not have the economic empowerment.”

- *Informal waste picker, Kenya*

Additionally, waste pickers often travel several kilometres each day to collect enough materials yet still struggle to earn enough to support their families (Fair Circularity Initiative, 2024).

3.3. UNCERTAIN MARKET ACCESS

Sudden policy changes or new regulations can disrupt waste markets and eliminate key waste streams. Policymakers and regulators often implement new regulations and related guidelines without meaningful consultation with waste pickers, due to limited understanding of on-the-ground realities (Sambyal, 2024). In many cases, profit-driven private entities take over waste management processes, displacing waste pickers and erasing their critical role in the recycling chain (Sambyal, 2024). For instance, the implementation of Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) regulations has significantly altered waste flows (Sambyal, 2024). Materials that were once considered valuable “waste”—collected, sorted, and sold by waste pickers at landfills—are now intercepted earlier in the supply chain by producers or formal recycling systems. As a result, recyclables no longer reach landfill sites, leading to income losses for waste pickers who rely on these materials (Shift, 2022). In some cases, waste pickers arrive at landfill sites only to find that the waste has already been sorted and removed, leaving them with little or nothing to collect. Lastly, even without new regulations, there is often high competition among waste pickers, which often creates situations of uncertainty (Fair Circularity Initiative, 2024).

“Policies should ensure fair pay to waste pickers as well as ensuring they benefit from EPR schemes.”

- *Informal waste picker, Kenya*

3.4. FEAR OF FORMAL INSTITUTIONS AND LACK OF FORMAL INCLUSION

Waste picking is predominantly an informal sector activity (Morais et al., 2022). In many countries—including Bangladesh, Cameroon, Côte d’Ivoire, Ethiopia, Ghana, Guinea-Bissau, Kenya, Malawi, Mongolia, Mozambique, Nicaragua, Pakistan, Nigeria, Palestine, the Philippines, Uganda, and Zimbabwe—it is largely absent from formal policy frameworks (Morais et al., 2022). This lack of recognition limits access to social protections, training opportunities, and financial support (Morais et al., 2022; Paul et al., 2012; Shift, 2022). Mistrust of official systems and fear of legal repercussions—particularly in contexts where national laws prohibit entry into landfills or collection sites—further discourage engagement (Kain et al., 2022). Additionally, many waste pickers lack national identification, restricting access to banking, social services, and formal employment. Refugees face even greater barriers, as fear of interacting with authorities perpetuates informality (Zisopoulos et al., 2023).

Without formal recognition, waste pickers remain excluded from programmes aimed at professionalization, leaving their future roles uncertain and vulnerable. Although informal waste workers coexist with municipal waste systems, collaboration may be minimal and often ineffective (Paul et al., 2012). The absence of formalization also undermines their ability to establish cooperatives, associations, or trade unions that are legally recognized and capable of supporting collective bargaining (Shift, 2022).

3.5. LIMITED EDUCATION AND TRAINING

“Most of what I know and use in my work is learned by daily experience without any formal training. A lot of trial and error.”

- *Informal waste picker, Kenya*

Waste pickers often lack access to formal education and technical training, which significantly limits their opportunities for advancement or entry into formal employment (Morais et al., 2022; Paul et al., 2012). Some are also illiterate (Barford & Ahmad, 2021). This knowledge gap not only restricts their earning potential but also

exposes them to health and safety risks. Specifically, training on the safe handling of hazardous materials, proper use of protective equipment, and techniques for identifying and sorting valuable recyclables is largely unavailable.

3.6. CHILD LABOUR/GENERATIONAL WASTE PICKING

Child labour remains widespread in waste picking, and children involved in this work are frequently exposed to hazardous materials (Barford & Ahmad, 2021; Shift, 2022). In many cases, children accompany their parents because families cannot afford childcare (Shift, 2022). This situation

“I have been working as a waste picker since I was 10 years old. For almost 20 years now.”

- *Informal waste picker, Kenya*

perpetuates cycles of poverty, limits access to education, and severely restricts long-term social mobility. The practice is often generational; children of waste pickers are highly likely to follow the same path. Few programmes exist to support the transition of children into formal education, and many parents lack the financial means to send their children to school (Barford & Ahmad, 2021; Schenck, Blaauw, Viljoen, et al., 2019). As a result, children continue working in dangerous conditions instead of pursuing opportunities

that could break this cycle of poverty.

“We are trying to see that our kids don’t come to the landfill. If you are a waste picker, you can almost be sure your kids will come because you cannot pay school fees.”

- *Informal waste picker, Kenya*

3.7. GENDER-BASED

VULNERABILITIES

Although not always the case (Schenck, Blaauw, Viljoen, et al., 2019), the informal waste sector is often predominantly female, which heightens risks of abuse, exploitation, and unsafe working conditions (Buch et al., 2021). Gender-sensitive protections are minimal, and social stigma deepens these challenges. Women frequently face discrimination, limited access to training, and a lack of childcare support, making it harder to secure stable livelihoods. They may also receive lower rates for materials compared to men (GIZ, 2011). Personal safety and security are major concerns, particularly when waste collection occurs at night (Schenck, Blaauw, Viljoen, et al., 2019; Shift, 2022). Additionally, access to basic sanitation facilities is often restricted, disproportionately affecting women and exacerbating health risks (Shift, 2022).

3.8. SOCIAL CHALLENGES, STIGMA, AND TENSIONS

In many countries, waste pickers are seen as playing a valuable role in society, yet they are often frequently looked down upon, ignored, or mistreated (Barford & Ahmad, 2021; Kain et al., 2022; Shift, 2022). Stigma and harassment—sometimes from authorities—continue to marginalize them (Morais et al., 2022). Criminal gangs exploit the informality of the sector, reinforcing negative perceptions and creating security risks (Schenck, Blaauw, Viljoen, et al., 2019). Waste pickers themselves are frequently and incorrectly associated with criminality, facing abuse, insults, and harassment, and the absence of labour rights and collective representation leaves workers vulnerable (Morais et al., 2022). Additionally, tensions or violence among waste pickers can occur (Schenck, Blaauw, Viljoen, et al., 2019). Other social challenges, such as racial conflict, infighting, theft, and substance abuse, are also prevalent (Schenck, Blaauw, Viljoen, et al., 2019).

“...waste pickers are usually at the bottom of the pyramid...”

- *Informal waste picker, Kenya*

3.9. LACK OF/INADEQUATE INFRASTRUCTURE

At the individual level, waste pickers often lack essential tools to perform their work efficiently, such as equipment for transporting waste or space to store recyclables before sale (Shift, 2022). At a broader level, waste segregation and recycling infrastructure remain inadequate, leading to improper disposal and environmental hazards (Paul et al., 2012; Sambyal, 2024). While informal systems operate without policy support, they play a crucial role in reducing waste volumes. However, these systems are rarely recognized or provided with the infrastructure needed to function effectively (Paul et al., 2012). For example, the absence of zonation at dumpsites forces waste collectors to sort through mixed waste to find resalable

“This job may seem simple, but it comes with many challenges. Income is unstable, and equipment is lacking. Many residents are not yet used to sorting waste, so our work becomes more labor-intensive”

- *Informal waste picker, Vietnam*

materials, making their work more time-consuming and inefficient. Furthermore, there is typically a lack of information hubs to disseminate knowledge and innovations related to waste management.

3.10. ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS AND RISKS

Improper disposal practices lead to soil, water, and air pollution; for example, burning plastics releases toxic gases (Morais et al., 2022). Informal waste management can also cause contamination through leaching into land and water, harming groundwater and nearby ecosystems (Paul et al., 2012). These risks are even more severe when dealing with hazardous or electronic waste, where improper recycling poses significant threats to both the environment and human health. Non-biodegradable waste accumulates over time, degrading land quality and increasing health hazards (Morais et al., 2022).

4. HUMANITARIAN WASTE PICKING INITIATIVES

Humanitarian and development actors have introduced numerous initiatives to promote sustainable livelihoods for informal waste pickers, often as part of broader waste management and circular economy programmes. Building on these efforts, WORM highlights practical examples—both from its consortium and beyond—and distils key characteristics to inform the development of a standardized policy framework that integrates waste-picking components into humanitarian livelihood strategies.

4.1. EXAMPLES FROM PRACTICE

“Community-led waste management”

Led by CRS in partnership with the Bureau for Humanitarian Assistance (BHA), the project aimed at establishing community-led waste management together with youth groups. Since mid-2022, six youth groups from different communities have been mobilized to collect, sort, and repurpose waste, supported by training in composting, recycling, and income-generating opportunities. The project integrates reverse logistics and piloting activities (e.g., baler system to compress sorted waste to transport to recycling facilities), with the intention of securing sustainable recycling partnerships.

“Scaling up a socialised model of domestic waste and plastic management in 5 cities”

Led by several local partners in Vietnam, including the Women’s Union of Da Nang City, Quy Nhon City, Binh Duong, and Binh Thuan Province, and the Quang Ninh Province Farmer’s Union, this project (2019-2022) aimed to improve solid waste management and introduce circular economy principles in five cities in Vietnam. The project engaged 1,786 informal waste pickers, primarily women and vulnerable individuals, through 42 targeted training sessions, boosting their income by at least 20%. Participants were

supported with bicycles and trolleys to support more efficient waste collection. Additionally, 18 clubs and groups were established to strengthen collective action and representation. By linking informal waste streams with municipal systems and improving their working conditions, the project enhanced their role in waste segregation and plastic reduction, while simultaneously raising public awareness and influencing policy reforms toward inclusive, sustainable waste management.

“Fair recycling project”

A collaborative effort between the Danish Refugee Council (DRC), Mr. Green Africa, and Unilever, this project (2021-2024) aimed to develop an inclusive plastic recycling ecosystem in Kenya by integrating informal waste pickers and refugees into a formalized plastics recycling value chain. To do so, they addressed two major challenges: plastic pollution and the economic marginalization of refugees and informal waste pickers. They provided training, safer working conditions, and income opportunities to drive the transition to a localized circular plastic economy through several interventions, including identifying and registering 1,500 waste pickers, transforming 500 waste pickers into collector agents, and developing pilot interventions. A key component of the project was also enrolling refugees in employment programmes as waste pickers, where the gathered plastic was then purchased by Unilever and recycled into new consumer products in Kenya.

“Closing the loop on humanitarian waste management using sustainable procurement and innovative finance”

Led by the International Organization for Migration (IOM), this project sought to develop an innovative financing mechanism to ensure that more waste generated as a result of humanitarian response is repaired and recycled. Local leadership and ownership are key for any innovation process to reach impact and have been a central part of this project as well. One central element has been a call for partnerships open to waste pickers, local repair shops, and recycling businesses, etc. Waste pickers have been supported in developing their applications. The waste pickers that won contracts have prioritized buying motorcycles for easier transportation of waste, phones for communication, and digital management of their waste picking activities and safety equipment. This project is also piloting the use of waste credits, an innovative financing mechanism in the same family as carbon credits.

“E-waste – Circular economy at scale”

Also led by IOM, this project aimed to develop a sustainable ecosystem to address the challenge of e-waste generated by humanitarian response. To be sustainable, any circular economy business model needs a certain scale and volume of waste. Waste pickers are key to achieving this. The established cooperative includes members from both the refugee and host communities. The cooperative oversees collecting e-waste and damaged electronics. Members have also received training in repairing broken solar lamps. The current scaling strategy includes an expansion of repair services to also include other electronics. The cooperative has now been legally registered in Uganda.

“Waste 4 value”

Led by Norwegian Church Aid (NCA), this project focused on designing sustainable circular economy business models around plastic waste. It started in Ethiopia, focusing on what it would take to develop a financially self-sustainable business model, and is now scaling across several countries. A core element of this business model is waste picker collectives. They have been supported with a broad range of training, including waste management and business management, and legal registration.

4.2. MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF EXISTING PROJECTS

Building on the projects described above, WORM also reviewed additional initiatives from end-users and the broader humanitarian sector to identify cross-cutting patterns related to key drivers, challenges, activities, and lessons learned. These are outlined in the following paragraphs.

Main drivers

- **Address environmental concerns:** All projects recognized the need to address growing environmental concerns, especially related to rising waste volumes and harmful practices like burning and mixing hazardous materials, as well as e-waste.
- **Create livelihood opportunities:** Initiatives sought to provide income for vulnerable groups—e.g., youth, women, elderly, refugees—who often work in waste picking, lack social protection, and face significant livelihood risks.
- **Enhance community engagement:** Efforts focused on promoting sustainable waste management, circular economy practices, and dialogue with waste pickers, while fostering collaboration within communities and among waste pickers themselves.
- **Integrate waste management into the humanitarian context:** Some projects incorporated waste sorting and recycling into emergency and development responses, such as training populations in refugee camps to improve living conditions and reduce health risk, or finding innovative ways to handle humanitarian waste.

Challenges

- **Low awareness:** Communities, including youth, often lack knowledge about proper waste sorting, handling, and environmental impacts (e.g., open burning) and many collectors are hesitant to adopt new methods.
- **Limited or lacking infrastructure:** Limited facilities for segregation and recycling, such as centralized sorting points, remain a major barrier.
- **Financial and technical constraints:** High equipment costs, limited budgets, and insufficient resources for training, product support, and communication hinder sustainability. Models often depend on international funding, making them vulnerable to disruption.
- **Risks related to hazardous waste:** The presence of hazardous waste adds another layer of difficulty—knowledge on safe handling is often lacking, and hazardous materials are frequently mixed with general waste, increasing risks.
- **Coordination gaps:** Poor integration between segregation, collection, and treatment reduces efficiency. For example, mixed waste collection by trucks undermines household-level sorting efforts.
- **Policy and market challenges:** Absence of regulations recognizing freelance waste collectors limits social protection. Competition with other informal operators can reduce income for participants.

Activities

- **Training and knowledge building:** Education on sorting, composting, and recycling was central to improving waste handling practices. Training also covered identifying and separating waste at disposal points to reduce landfill volumes.
- **Infrastructure and equipment:** Projects provided waste pickers with essential tools (e.g., bicycles, sorting carts) and protective gear (e.g., gloves, masks, boots) to enhance efficiency and safety.
- **Community empowerment:** Initiatives engaged local actors—governments, unions, and communities—to co-design projects and raise awareness. Some targeted households for source separation and organized city recycling points (“green houses”) for residents to deposit recyclables. Practices varied by context; for example, household-level collection was common in Vietnam but rare in Kenya due to stigma.
- **Cash-for-work vs. transition models:** Short-term employment addressed immediate needs but lacked sustainability. Some projects offered livelihood transition support, such as loans for equipment or small businesses (e.g., street food carts).

- **Linking livelihoods:** Successful models connected waste picking with recycling and upcycling enterprises, creating income streams and promoting self-reliance. Participants also learned to transform waste into products (e.g., plastic chairs, plant pots) for resale or to repair and reuse existing ones.
- **Policy influence:** Several projects shaped local regulations and promoted the formal inclusion of waste pickers. In Vietnam, government-led initiatives with humanitarian partners facilitated smoother integration of project outcomes into policy.

Lessons learned

- **Plan for scale and sustainability:** Projects should analyse waste volumes, recycling, and reuse potential early. Current models rely heavily on sponsored funding, with no stable budget. Fluctuating prices for recyclables often disrupt fundraising and reduce participation. Building self-managed organizations with clear, flexible operating mechanisms and community engagement was a key lesson learned across several projects.
- **Address community barriers:** Engage community leaders to drive participation and influence behavioural change. Empower core group leaders to supervise activities and prioritize youth engagement for long-term impact. Persistent habits—such as littering, poor source segregation, and reliance on disposable plastics—remain major challenges.
- **Ensure comprehensive coordination:** Expand beyond humanitarian waste to include all waste streams for long-term sustainability. Strengthen coordination among sectors (environment, tourism, education, women’s unions) and build partnerships with private enterprises for recycling and eco-product development. Work with international organizations and sponsors to adopt green technologies suited to local conditions.
- **Secure adequate resources:** Waste management is often overlooked in humanitarian budgets. Allocate sufficient funding and staff for projects, including training and capacity building for grassroots leaders on communication, self-management, and environmental monitoring.
- **Monitor and share lessons:** Establish mechanisms for regular monitoring, evaluation, and documentation of challenges, successes, and lessons learned. Share findings widely to enable replication. Recognize and reward active individuals and groups to sustain momentum. Promote environmental education through social media, schools, and community activities. Organize competitions and campaigns to foster engagement.

5. SUSTAINABLE LIVELIHOODS FRAMEWORK (SLF)

The Sustainable Livelihoods Framework (SLF), developed by the UK Department for International Development (DFID) in 1999, is widely used to understand and analyse livelihoods in low-income countries and to assess the effectiveness of poverty reduction efforts (DFID, 1999). The term “livelihood” goes beyond income generation (Dias, 2016); it encompasses the capabilities, assets (both material and social), and activities required for a means of living, which are also dynamic.

As illustrated in Figure 2, a livelihood is considered sustainable when it can withstand and recover from stresses and shocks, maintain or enhance its capabilities and assets over time, and do so without undermining the natural resource base (DFID, 1999). In the following sections, we describe the theoretical background behind the components of the model and then relate it to the informal waste-picking context.

Figure 2 Sustainable Livelihoods Framework (SLF). Adapted from (DFID, 1999).

5.1. VULNERABILITY CONTEXT

Understanding vulnerability is essential in any given context. The *vulnerability context* refers to external factors—such as political, policy, and socioeconomic conditions—that shape livelihoods but remain largely beyond individual control. These factors are driven by trends (e.g., political shifts), shocks (e.g., conflict), or seasonality (e.g., price fluctuations) (DFID, 1999). For example, when formal employment is unavailable, many turn to informal urban economies like waste picking, while conflict can further marginalize already poor groups (DFID, 1999). Waste pickers face many challenges and risks, as presented in Section 3. Some are inherent risks, such as exposure to dirt, pollution, and toxic materials, as well as preventable risks like lack of PPE or exposure to criminal exploitation, which can be mitigated through better management practices (Schenck, Blaauw, Swart, et al., 2019).

5.2. LIVELIHOOD ASSETS

Livelihood assets refer to the resources, capabilities, and strengths people draw upon within their context. In the SLF, these assets are grouped into five interrelated categories: human, social, natural, physical, and financial (DFID, 1999).

Human Capital

Human capital represents the abilities, experience, work skills, and the physical state of good health which, when combined, allow populations to engage with different strategies and fulfil their own objectives for their livelihoods. Human capital is a building block to achieving livelihood outcomes and is necessary to make use of the other four livelihood assets (DFID, 1999).

Social Capital

Social capital refers to the networks and relationships people rely on to sustain and improve their livelihoods, including networks and connectedness, membership of more formalised groups, and relationships of trust, reciprocity, and exchanges (DFID, 1999). In the context of sustainable livelihoods for waste pickers, local social capital includes family support, community associations, local authorities, and peer networks among waste pickers (Schenck, Blaauw, Swart, et al., 2019).

Natural Capital

Natural capital refers to naturally occurring resources—such as soil, water, air, and genetic resources—that can be used as inputs to generate benefits, including food production, protection against soil or coastal erosion, and other ecosystem services that support livelihoods (DFID, 1999). Natural capital is closely linked to the vulnerability context, as shocks that undermine livelihoods often also degrade natural resources (DFID, 1999).

Physical Capital

Physical capital refers to the basic infrastructure and material resources that support livelihoods, such as affordable transport, secure shelter, clean water, sanitation, energy, and access to information (DFID, 1999), which are often lacking for informal waste pickers. The primary physical asset for waste pickers is access to recyclable waste at landfills, which provides income. Beyond recyclables, landfills offer other valuable items—food, clothing, household goods, furniture, and electronic devices—either for personal use or resale. Access to these resources depends on landfill management practices. Basic facilities, such as shaded areas for sorting and storing recyclables, are also critical for improving working conditions and dignity (Schenck, Blaauw, Swart, et al., 2019).

Financial Capital

Lastly, *financial capital* refers to the financial resources people use to achieve their livelihood objectives, including available stocks (e.g., savings) and regular inflow of money (e.g., stable income) (DFID, 1999). For waste pickers, landfill work is often the only available option due to low entry barriers (Schenck, Blaauw, Swart, et al., 2019). A key advantage they cite is access to “daily income” or “quick money,” though earnings are highly unstable and vary by factors such as the volume and accessibility of recyclables, weather conditions, health, and fluctuating market prices. This volatility underscores the precarious nature of waste picking as a livelihood (Schenck, Blaauw, Swart, et al., 2019)

5.3. TRANSFORMING STRUCTURES AND PROCESSES

Transforming structures and processes within the SLF refers to the institutions, organizations, policies, and legislation that shape how people access resources and pursue livelihoods. These operate at all levels—from households to international arenas—and influence access to assets, terms of exchange, and returns on livelihood strategies (DFID, 1999). They also affect inclusion, well-being, and cultural norms. For waste pickers, these structures determine when and how they can collect and sell recyclables. Key actors include municipalities, private waste management companies, and buy-back centres (BBCs), which play a critical role in enabling waste collection and trade (Schenck, Blaauw, Swart, et al., 2019). Price structures at BBCs are complex, influenced by transport costs, material quality, and global market fluctuations (Schenck, Blaauw, Swart, et al., 2019). In the case of this deliverable, humanitarian organizations are included as part of transforming structures and processes.

5.4. LIVELIHOOD STRATEGIES

Livelihood strategies refer to the activities and decisions individuals undertake to achieve their livelihood goals, including productive activities, investment strategies, and reproductive choices (DFID, 1999). The livelihoods approach seeks to promote choice, opportunity, and diversity (DFID, 1999).

For waste pickers, landfill work is sometimes the only viable income source due to limited skills, lack of qualifications, and barriers to formal employment such as age, poor health, or missing identification documents (Schenck, Blaauw, Swart, et al., 2019). Many choose this work to avoid crime or idleness, maintain independence, or supplement seasonal income. Their routine involves early visits to landfills, sometimes sleeping on-site, and collecting high-value recyclables like scrap metal and plastic. Others gather items for personal use or resale. Often, recyclables are sold to BBCs, though informal sales often

yield lower returns. This strategy demonstrates adaptability and resilience amid economic and social constraints (Schenck, Blaauw, Swart, et al., 2019).

5.5. LIVELIHOOD OUTCOMES

Livelihood outcomes are the achievements resulting from livelihood strategies. The livelihoods framework emphasizes understanding these outcomes without assuming income maximization as the sole goal; instead, it recognizes diverse priorities such as security, well-being, and resilience (DFID, 1999). Waste pickers' outcomes are shaped by historical and political contexts (Dias, 2016) and can be assessed through five dimensions (Schenck, Blaauw, Swart, et al., 2019; Scoones, 2009):

- **Creation of working days:** Waste picking provides flexible, regular work, allowing individuals to earn a daily income and balance family responsibilities.
- **Poverty reduction:** Income from recyclables sustains households, though improvements in governance, access to materials, and safer conditions could enhance earnings, moving waste pickers out of poverty.
- **Subjective well-being:** Livelihoods should enhance well-being. For waste pickers, well-being is positively influenced by factors such as income, a sense of agency, and social connections. Conversely, inadequate safety, lack of support, and absence of dignity contribute to poor well-being.
- **Capability development:** Skills are acquired informally through experience and peer learning, including knowledge of sorting, pricing, and market dynamics. This can also include learning from each other.
- **Recovery from setbacks:** Livelihood sustainability is threatened by landfill closures, technological changes, and policy shifts.

These outcomes reflect adaptability and resilience but also the fact that waste pickers remain vulnerable to systemic constraints (Schenck, Blaauw, Swart, et al., 2019). In reference to the policy framework in this document, they can also be seen as an initial set of indicators to assess the success of the programme (discussed further below).

6. POLICY FRAMEWORK: SUSTAINABLE LIVELIHOODS FOR WASTE PICKERS

To address the challenges outlined above, WORM proposes a policy framework for sustainable humanitarian livelihood programmes that integrate social, economic, and environmental dimensions of informal waste pickers' sustainability. This framework builds existing initiatives and incorporates best practices informed by stakeholder engagement through workshops, site visits, and interviews. It is further complemented by insights from academic and grey literature, as well as innovative business models and the SLF presented in the previous section. The following pages outline the guiding principles, step-by-step approach, roles and responsibilities, and integration into innovative business models.

6.1. GUIDING PRINCIPLES

Guiding principles are core values that shape a programme's design, implementation, and evaluation. They serve as an ethical and strategic compass, ensuring alignment with goals such as dignity, inclusion, sustainability, and empowerment. These principles are universal and enduring, applicable across contexts and stages of a programme. In this section, we introduce eight guiding principles for developing humanitarian livelihood programmes that support sustainable livelihoods for informal waste pickers.

Table 1 illustrates how the guiding principles address each of the challenges described in Section 3, as well as the corresponding type of capital from the SLF under the umbrella of “Livelihood Asset”. Due to the nature of the humanitarian programmes, Livelihood Assets are most likely to be where most of the attention towards interventions is placed. This linkage demonstrates that addressing challenges faced by waste pickers also requires strengthening a specific form of capital through principles that promote dignity, inclusion, economic viability, sustainability, and empowerment.

Table 1: Challenges faced by informal waste pickers, linked to guiding principles and corresponding types of capital under the SLF (DFID, 1999), with examples.

CHALLENGE	GUIDING PRINCIPLE	LIVELIHOOD ASSET	EXAMPLE
Risk to health and safety	Dignity, health, and safety	Human capital, Social capital	Safe working conditions reduce hazards
Income insecurity and exploitation	Economic inclusion and diversification	Financial capital	Stable income, reduce vulnerability
Uncertain market access	Economic inclusion and diversification	Financial capital, Social capital	Market linkages, improve resilience
Fear of formal institutions and lack of formal inclusion	Formal recognition and advocacy	Social capital	Rights, legal protection, social legitimacy
Lack of education and training	Education, training, and capacity building	Human capital	Skills development, empowerment
Child labour and generational waste picking	Economic inclusion and diversification, Education, training, and capacity building	Human capital, Financial capital	Breaking poverty cycles, child protection
Gender-based vulnerabilities	Dignity, health, and safety	Human capital, Social capital	Equity, safety, empowerment
Social perception, stigma, and tensions	Formal recognition and advocacy	Social capital	Destigmatization, social cohesion
Lack of/inadequate infrastructure	Local approaches based on local contexts	Physical capital	Infrastructure for sorting, storage, and transport
Lack of integration into formal waste systems	Economic inclusion and diversification, Formal recognition and advocacy	Social capital	Inclusion in municipal systems
Environmental impacts	Environmental stewardship	Natural capital	Waste reduction, climate resilience

Dignity, health, and safety

Sustainable humanitarian livelihood programmes for informal waste pickers must prioritize dignity, health, and safety as foundational principles. Participation should be voluntary, with safeguards to prevent exploitation, harassment, and discrimination. Programmes should ensure fair and transparent remuneration, respect for workers' rights, and mechanisms for grievance redressal. Core measures include providing adequate PPE, first aid, clean water, sanitation facilities, and occupational safety training. Access to healthcare services and psychosocial support should also be considered to address the physical and mental health risks associated with waste picking (Schenck, Blaauw, Viljoen, et al., 2019).

A gender-sensitive approach is also essential, actively engaging women and addressing their specific vulnerabilities, alongside other marginalized groups such as persons with disabilities, children, and minorities. Child labour prevention must be integrated, complemented by measures that support parents through education initiatives and childcare services to break the intergenerational cycle of waste picking (Barford & Ahmad, 2021; Morais et al., 2022).

Co-design, empowerment, and collective action

Waste pickers already often organize themselves in groups such as youth groups, women groups, extended family groups, membership-based organizations (MBOs), cooperatives, associations, networks, or microenterprises (Kain et al., 2022). These waste picker organizations are crucial to unite waste pickers under a common voice to strengthen bargaining power, improve incomes and working conditions, and facilitate integration into formal waste systems (Buch et al., 2021; Dias, 2016; Shift, 2022). They also promote knowledge sharing, community engagement, and social equity. Programme design and beneficiary selection should also be transparent and inclusive.

Whether building off an existing initiative or starting from scratch, programmes must be co-designed with waste pickers to ensure relevance, accountability, and respect for human rights. Meaningful participation in planning, implementation, and evaluation fosters ownership, trust, and empowerment, while recognizing the dignity and expertise of waste pickers (Dias, 2016). Their input is critical for identifying risks and designing effective mitigation measures, ensuring that interventions reflect real challenges and opportunities they face (Shift, 2022). Engaging with waste pickers throughout the entire process—from planning and design to implementation and evaluation—ensures that historically marginalized voices are heard and respected (Barford & Ahmad, 2021). Since waste pickers will ideally continue this work independently after the project/programme ends, early and meaningful involvement is critical to foster ownership and long-term sustainability (Dias, 2016; Shift, 2022).

Formal recognition and advocacy

Formal recognition and advocacy are essential for securing the rights, dignity, and long-term inclusion of waste pickers within municipal and legal systems. Legal recognition allows access to identification documents, social protection schemes, municipal services, and legal protections—all critical elements for improving livelihoods and reducing vulnerability (Morais et al., 2022). When designed inclusively, formalization can transform precarious work into dignified livelihoods by providing legal protections, safe working conditions, and access to infrastructure, equipment, and financial services (Barford & Ahmad, 2021; Morais et al., 2022). However, formalization policies vary widely across contexts and can fail to deliver these benefits (Morais et al., 2022). Poorly designed transitions, e.g., driven by privatization, can marginalize the poorest and exacerbate inequalities (da Silva et al., 2019)

Thus, formalization and advocacy must prioritize participatory approaches, ensuring that the formalization processes are shaped by waste pickers themselves through a clear theory of change (Morais et al., 2022). Advocacy should dismantle stigma and promote social legitimacy through public awareness and policy dialogue. Integration into municipal systems and participation in circular economy initiatives should position waste pickers as key actors in sustainable resource management. Formal recognition and

advocacy must prioritize health, safety, and representation, ensuring that systemic change invests in people, not just material flows (Morais et al., 2022).

Economic inclusion and diversification

Economic inclusion and livelihood diversification are critical for sustainable livelihood programmes for waste pickers. While waste picking offers immediate income for those with limited alternatives, true sustainability requires creating pathways for economic empowerment and resilience. Economic inclusion means ensuring waste pickers can participate in and benefit from the broader recycling value chain without mandatory formalization, which can create barriers when not designed properly (as described above, although formality may be required to reach certain benefits).

Livelihood diversification emphasizes expanding opportunities beyond waste picking through value-added activities such as sorting, baling, and upcycling, as well as fostering entrepreneurship and market linkages. These approaches strengthen income security, foster integration into formal waste systems (when appropriate), and build resilience against market fluctuations (Dias, 2016). Importantly, engagement with private and public sector actors must go beyond improving recycling practices and material flows to investing in the people who sustain these systems. Circularity should evolve to integrate social equity, fair pricing, and health and safety standards, ensuring that economic inclusion and diversification are not only environmental goals but also human-centred imperatives (Barford & Ahmad, 2021; Zisopoulos et al., 2023).

Education, training, and capacity building

Education, training, and capacity building are essential to empower waste pickers and break cycles of poverty and informality (Barford & Ahmad, 2021; Buch et al., 2021). These principles ensure waste pickers can work safely, negotiate fair prices, and participate effectively in waste value chains. Training should cover safe handling of materials, sorting techniques, occupational health and safety, and business development skills (Barford & Ahmad, 2021). Beyond technical skills, capacity building should also include negotiation and, where relevant, leadership training. These skills enable waste pickers to advocate for better working conditions, secure fair prices for recyclables, and build constructive relationships with stakeholders—strengthening their livelihoods while promoting dignity and respect for their work (ILO, 2025b). Additionally, digital literacy and financial management training can open pathways to entrepreneurship and economic resilience.

Education may also extend to families: programmes should also support access to schooling for children and provide childcare options to prevent child labour and promote intergenerational mobility (Dias, 2016). Ultimately, education and capacity building should be continuous, participatory, and tailored to local contexts, ensuring that waste pickers are not only safer and more skilled but also recognized as key actors in a just and inclusive circular economy.

Local approaches based on local contexts

Effective and sustainable waste management approaches must be rooted in local realities. Localization means aligning livelihood programmes with the existing systems and business models, and collaborating with local authorities, non-government organizations (NGOs), and private sector actors to co-create policies, develop infrastructure, and implement inclusive circular initiatives (Velis, 2017).

As recycling value chains are highly diverse and context-specific, strategies should “be tailored to local contexts while guided by globally aligned principles” (Shift, 2022), as even well-resourced external interventions are unlikely to achieve lasting impact without first building sufficient local capacity (Velis, 2017). This may include investments in infrastructure such as Material Recovery Facilities (MRFs) (specialized plants that sort mixed recyclables into separate materials ready to be sold up the waste value chain, such as to manufacturers), designated work zones, or collection points. When waste pickers can manage parts of their own supply chain and engage in upstream collection, reliance on landfills

decreases—promoting social, economic, and environmental sustainability. However, it is necessary to keep in mind that not all solutions fit to each context.

Environmental stewardship

Environmental stewardship must be embedded in programme design. Informal waste pickers significantly contribute to plastic waste reduction and complement circular economy initiatives, even without formal policy support. Programmes should recognize and strengthen this role by promoting waste reduction, reuse, and recycling through awareness campaigns and training, while monitoring indicators such as reduced open dumping and improved segregation.

Transparency, monitoring, and continuous learning

Establishing clear standards, transparent data systems, and accessible grievance mechanisms is essential for ensuring accountability and trust in waste-picking programmes. Indicators should track safety compliance, income generation, participation, and environmental performance. Participatory feedback mechanisms empower beneficiaries and communities, while periodic reviews enable programmes to evolve based on lessons learned and changing contexts. This approach fosters continuous learning and adaptive management, allowing programmes to respond effectively to emerging challenges and enhance impact over time.

6.2. STEP-BY-STEP IMPLEMENTATION APPROACH

A structured, phased approach is essential for implementing sustainable humanitarian livelihood programmes that integrate informal waste picking. This approach ensures alignment with local contexts, maximizes impact, and mitigates risks. The following section provides practical, step-by-step guidance for humanitarian organizations and partners to operationalize the policy framework across diverse field settings. The goal is to design waste-picking programmes that are not only effective but also adaptable and sustainable over time. Using the SLF as a base, one could envision these steps as the transformation and transition between “transforming structures and processes” and “livelihood strategies” with the goal of achieving positive “livelihood outcomes”.

The phases presented below can be adjusted to accommodate various sizes of programmes, depending on the first phase: goal and scope. The next three phases—stakeholder identification, data collection, and waste value chain mapping—are adapted from the methodology outlined by HELP Logistics (HELP Logistics, 2024)³. These are followed by subsequent steps: programme design and planning; formalization and legal recognition; capacity building and training; infrastructure and equipment provision; market engagement and value chain development; and finally, monitoring, evaluation, and adaptation.

Steps three and four are included as optional components for projects aiming to understand the broader waste management systems and comprehensively integrate informal waste systems into formal streams—particularly relevant when the goal is to formalize waste pickers, establish cooperatives, or strengthen local governance structures. For humanitarian programmes with a narrower focus on supporting waste pickers at a smaller scale, these steps can be streamlined by moving directly from Step

³ Please see the supplementary material entitled, “Local Waste Value Chain Mapping Methodology for the Humanitarian Sector” as well as the Excel file, “Waste Chain Mapping”, developed by HELP Logistics. *Note:* This approach was developed by HELP Logistics during an exploratory project in 2024 and is shared for reference only. It has not been tested, validated, or formalized as an official HELP product. Its inclusion is intended to support D6.2 and organizations developing humanitarian livelihood programs with a waste-picking component. This does not imply maturity, endorsement, or ongoing support from HELP Logistics.

2: Stakeholder identification, to Step 5: Programme design and planning. Please see Figure 3 below for an illustration of these steps aligned with guiding principles and identifying relevant stakeholders.

Figure 3 Key components for sustainable livelihood programme development, including guiding principles, step-by-step approach, and relevant stakeholders.

1. Goal and scope

The first and most critical step in any project or programme is to clearly define its overall goal and scope, as these elements provide the foundation for all subsequent planning and implementation activities. A well-defined goal articulates the intended impact—such as improving livelihoods, reducing environmental harm, or integrating informal waste systems—while the scope specifies the boundaries of the intervention, including geographic coverage, target groups, and key activities.

Importantly, both the goal and scope should be considered dynamic rather than fixed. They may evolve over time as new data emerges, stakeholder priorities shift, or contextual challenges arise. This flexibility ensures that the programme remains relevant and responsive to changing conditions. When setting the goal and scope, various factors may come into play, such as: (1) alignment with broader organizational objectives; (2) stakeholder priorities (including donors); (3) resource availability; (4) timeframe; and (5) risk management.

2. Stakeholder identification and preliminary assessment

Identifying key actors in the waste value chain under study—from waste generators and pickers to those adding value through recycling or transformation, such as existing waste management actors, municipal services, and private contractors—is a critical step in programme design. The process begins with desk research to map active stakeholders, drawing on reports from government agencies, NGOs, academic studies, and, when possible/necessary, interviews with local experts (HELP Logistics, 2024). It is also important to understand the hierarchies within which waste pickers operate, as these structures can vary

by context (Barford & Ahmad, 2021). Early engagement fosters trust and ensures programme legitimacy (Zapata Campos et al., 2023).

In addition to identifying stakeholders, a preliminary stakeholder assessment should be conducted early in the planning stage to identify potential supporters and hindering forces to empower informal waste pickers and pathways to strengthen the integration of informal waste systems (Paul et al., 2012). These partnerships are vital for humanitarian organizations, as they enable the development and implementation of waste management strategies that are culturally appropriate, economically feasible, and technically sound (HELP Logistics, 2024). Alongside stakeholder identification, the preliminary study should also identify the types of waste generated and collected in the area to inform programme design and resource allocation (HELP Logistics, 2024).

3. Data collection

Step three entails collecting detailed information on the waste system under study (i.e., depending on the scope of study). This includes:

- Information on local waste generation (e.g., volumes), as well as collection and disposal practices
- Potential challenges and opportunities within the sector (e.g., SWOT analysis)

This step builds off stakeholder identification to better understand their roles within the system. Each stakeholder should provide data on the type of waste they generate or collect, sources, disposal methods, and/or subsequent links in the supply chain. These inputs will also be used to develop the waste value chain map. Additionally, data will offer insights into stakeholder capacity, local business practices, and logistics—providing a comprehensive understanding of the local waste management landscape to guide practical planning and project design (HELP Logistics, 2024).

4. Waste value chain mapping

The next step involves conducting a rapid assessment of the local waste landscape, including types of waste generated, existing collection systems, and market demand for recyclables. This assessment brings together steps two (stakeholders) and three (waste flows) to include:

- Types of waste generated, their sources, and volumes
- Existing collection and disposal systems, including formal and informal actors
- Market demand for recyclables and collected materials

Understanding the waste value chain also helps to identify opportunities to transform waste into resources (e.g., new products by integrating innovative business models) and divert materials from landfills without compromising the livelihoods of waste pickers. This assessment can also include identifying socio-economic conditions, gender dynamics, and environmental risks associated with the local waste management system (HELP Logistics, 2024)

Applying the methodology developed by HELP Logistics (2024) provides a structured framework for mapping complex waste systems in both urban and rural contexts. The approach is designed to achieve the following primary objectives:

- Systematically identify and document all stakeholders and processes within the waste chain,
- Create a visual map showing waste flows, stakeholder interactions, pricing structures, and key bottlenecks in the local recycling economy,
- Provide practical tools, including an Excel template for data organization and analysis, to support the field team.

5. Programme design and planning

Programme objectives, target groups, and expected outcomes must be clearly defined. Design and planning should also establish robust mechanisms for self-autonomy and long-term sustainability, as these have been consistently identified in the literature as major challenges for waste-picking initiatives (Kain et al., 2022). The detailed implementation plan should include:

- Main objectives of the project/programme
- Timeline and milestones for each phase
- Roles and responsibilities of implementing partners and stakeholders
- Resource requirements, including financial, human, and logistical inputs
- Compliance with local regulations and adherence to humanitarian standards

Specifically, a study by Paul et al. (2012) finds that the key factors for success include:

- Finding a **voice** (through organizing and collective action)
- Establishing **validity** (through legal status)
- Making the voice **visible** (through capacity building and awareness)
- Building a **viability** (through market linkages)

Thus, WORM proposes that this step be the starting point of finding the “voice”, with careful attention to inclusivity. Learnings from previous/existing projects indicate that it is also important to get buy-in from community leaders/appoint a local representative who can take ownership even after the project is complete. As described above, this should be a participatory process starting from the programme design and planning phase. Waste pickers and community representatives should be included from this point on to enhance relevance, ownership, and sustainability (Gutberlet & Carenzo, 2020).

6. Capacity building, training, and education

Training is a cornerstone of effective programme implementation, ensuring that both staff and beneficiaries have the knowledge and skills required for safe and sustainable waste management. Staff and community facilitators should receive instruction on safe waste handling, hygiene, occupational health and safety, and programme management. Beneficiaries, including waste pickers, need practical training in sorting, recycling techniques, and business skills to improve efficiency and income generation (Barford & Ahmad, 2021; Buch et al., 2021).

Capacity-building initiatives should be inclusive, participatory, and tailored to local contexts, with collaboration between government agencies, NGOs, and waste picker organizations (Sambyal, 2024). Key training areas include leadership development, organization-building, collective bargaining, policy compliance, and digital tools for traceability and reporting. Gender-sensitive and child protection modules must be integrated to address vulnerabilities (Shift, 2022), while partnerships with local waste management actors and government bodies strengthen regulatory compliance and long-term sustainability (Barford & Ahmad, 2021).

To sustain momentum, programmes should incorporate follow-up workshops, mentorship schemes, and cooperative-building efforts, alongside access to resources such as legal aid and communication tools. Awareness campaigns targeting the public and policymakers can promote circular economy principles and advocate for recognition and protection of waste pickers (ILO, 2025b). Documenting best practices and success stories helps demonstrate impact and attract further support from governmental and non-governmental actors.

Capacity strengthening should also focus on entrepreneurship and economic empowerment, addressing topics such as financial literacy, business development, market linkages, and cooperative management. These efforts enable waste pickers to diversify livelihoods, including micro-manufacturing products from recycled materials, and increase their stake in local and regional economies (Buch et al., 2021). Educational programmes for waste pickers’ families, particularly children, can improve long-term

prospects for formal employment and break cycles of poverty (Paul et al., 2012). While capacity building is listed here as a single step, it is not a one-time activity but a continuous process that combines technical training, organizational development, and mindset transformation. Thus, it is a step that will be continuously revisited throughout the duration of the programme/project.

7. Infrastructure and equipment provision

Operational success depends on adequate infrastructure. Programmes should prioritize the establishment of collection points, sorting stations, and storage facilities, complemented by investments in MRFs and designated work zones to improve material quality and reduce reliance on landfills. Addressing the persistent challenge of space for informal workers is critical, as waste picking often occurs in hazardous, overcrowded, or public spaces that are not recognized within conventional urban planning frameworks (Dias, 2016).

Provision of PPE, uniforms (also to establish legitimacy), and tools (e.g., carts) is essential to ensure health, safety, and dignity for waste pickers (Barford & Ahmad, 2021). Programmes should also implement health, safety, and hygiene protocols, including handwashing facilities, first aid kits, and training on safe waste handling and emergency procedures. Special attention must be given to hazardous and medical waste, supported by health monitoring systems that adapt protocols as risks evolve. Beyond operational infrastructure, programmes should invest in basic social services such as water supply, sanitation, childcare, and education to improve living conditions for waste picker communities (Paul et al., 2012).

To strengthen economic resilience, programmes should explore access to technology for remanufacturing and production, enabling waste picker cooperatives to move up the recycling value chain. Affordable, low-tech machinery—such as open-source equipment for shredding, extrusion, and moulding—can support micro-manufacturing of upcycled products like bags, furniture, and building materials. This approach shortens supply chains, reduces transportation costs, and creates new revenue streams, allowing cooperatives to diversify livelihoods and achieve financial sustainability (Buch et al., 2021). Partnerships with private sector actors and local authorities can facilitate the creation of decentralized micro-manufacturing hubs, transforming waste into marketable products and fostering community-based economic development (discussed in further steps).

8. Formalization and legal advocacy

Formalization is a critical step toward ensuring the recognition, protection, and empowerment of waste pickers within integrated waste management systems. This process begins with establishing a legal framework that acknowledges access to waste as a livelihood resource (Dias, 2016) and includes waste pickers in national and sub-national legislation (Barford & Ahmad, 2021; Sambyal, 2024). Legal recognition should be complemented by national certifications, occupational identity cards, and streamlined registration processes with reduced fees to facilitate inclusion in the formal economy.

Key measures for formalization include:

- Legal protection and social security schemes to safeguard livelihoods and address risks such as child labour and occupational hazards
- Provision of formal contracts or agreements for collection and environmental services, ensuring fair payment and clear responsibilities
- Integration into developing systems, e.g., EPR, with regulations defining roles for informal waste pickers/the informal recycling system and mandating their inclusion in waste management frameworks (Sambyal, 2024)

As described above, organizing waste pickers into cooperatives or associations is a proven strategy for achieving legitimacy and improving bargaining power. Cooperatives provide job security, better working conditions, resilience to economic shocks, and leadership opportunities for women. They also enable

waste pickers to negotiate access to waste streams and secure better prices from buyers, connecting them to formal supply chains (Buch et al., 2021).

International alliances and federations, such as the International Alliance of Waste Pickers (IAWP), play a vital role in promoting social and economic inclusion, advocating for laws and policies that involve waste pickers in decision-making, and supporting organizational development at scale (ILO, 2025a). The IAWP, for example, is a union of 50 organizations representing more than 460,000 waste pickers across 34 countries (ILO, 2025a). Local interventions should mirror these efforts by assisting with registration processes, providing membership benefits such as identification cards, health services, insurance, and access to finance (Paul et al., 2012). Formalization is not just about legal status but rather creating pathways for waste pickers to transition into the formal economy while still preserving their livelihoods.

9. Market engagement and value chain development

Connecting waste pickers to formal markets is also essential for ensuring long-term sustainability and economic empowerment. Programmes should facilitate linkages with local recycling businesses, cooperatives, and buyers, while exploring opportunities for value addition through activities such as upcycling, composting, and small-scale remanufacturing (Buch et al., 2021; Dias, 2016). Public-private partnerships (PPPs) and BBCs can create predictable demand, stabilize income streams, and foster integration into circular economy initiatives (Barford & Ahmad, 2021).

Successful market engagement requires building networks of stakeholders, including municipalities, private waste management companies, waste picker cooperatives, recyclers, academic institutions, and civil society organizations. Transparent and participatory decision-making processes ensure that waste pickers are recognized as key actors within integrated waste management systems. Identifying complementary roles for waste pickers—such as source segregation, door-to-door collection, and specialized recovery of recyclables—can improve waste diversion rates, reduce GHG emissions, and extend landfill lifespans, while enhancing income opportunities for waste pickers (Buch et al., 2021; Dias, 2016). Here, it is key to establish formal agreements with local businesses and cooperatives to absorb the waste collected by programme participants.

Programmes should also invest in awareness campaigns to highlight the economic and environmental benefits of waste picker integration, mobilizing public and political support to safeguard these systems against changing political priorities (Zapata Campos et al., 2023). Formal contracts and agreements between waste picker organizations and municipalities or private companies can further strengthen market access and provide security for service provision (Paul et al., 2012).

To maximize value creation, programmes should promote cooperative enterprise models and low-cost micro-manufacturing technologies that enable waste pickers to produce upcycled products from plastic and other recyclables. This approach not only diversifies livelihoods but also accelerates the transition to a circular economy by transforming waste into marketable goods such as furniture, building materials, and consumer products (Buch et al., 2021).

10. Monitoring, evaluation, adaptation, and outreach

A robust framework for monitoring, evaluation, and adaptive management should be established to track progress and set benchmarks for improvement. This framework can incorporate a range of indicators, such as livelihood outcomes, and more specific metrics drawn from existing projects (see Section 4), including the number of waste pickers engaged, provision of PPE and equipment, income generated, and activation of alternative income streams. Additionally, the process should include regular feedback sessions with key stakeholders—such as waste pickers, local governments, NGOs, and private sector actors—to enable adaptive management and continuous improvement. Finally, organizations should share learnings and results through outreach activities.

6.3. ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

Effective implementation of humanitarian waste-picking programmes requires clear delineation of roles among key actors to ensure coherence, accountability, and sustainability. Each programme/project will have context-specific factors that influence the level of responsibility and who will be responsible. In this section, we outline a non-exhaustive list of the general responsibilities of all potential actors, including humanitarian organizations/NGOs, local authorities/governments, the private sector, donors, and the wider community (including waste pickers).

Humanitarian organizations/NGOs (i.e., project lead)

Humanitarian organizations play a central role in initiating, designing, and managing programmes for sustainable livelihoods for waste pickers. Their responsibilities include:

- **Programme design and planning:** Lead the development of inclusive, context-specific programme plans that align with humanitarian principles, organizational objectives, and operational realities, together with the support of other actors (e.g., local authorities, other organizations, waste pickers).
- **Community engagement:** Identify and mobilize target groups for the programme/project, ensuring informed consent, and facilitating participation through community outreach.
- **Coordination:** Act as a bridge between communities, local authorities, and private sector partners to ensure collaborative implementation.
- **Capacity building and training:** Provide training on safe waste handling, market engagement, negotiation, leadership skills, and cooperative development; this may also be done in partnership with local actors, especially with the goal of being self-financed long-term.
- **Provision of PPE and equipment:** Provide waste pickers with sufficient PPE, uniforms, and other equipment to improve work safety and efficiency.
- **Protection measures:** Prioritize gender-sensitive programming, prevention of child labour, and safeguards for other vulnerable or marginalized groups.
- **Knowledge sharing:** Document and share lessons learned to promote evidence-based practices and increased community awareness for sustainable, inclusive waste management programmes.

Local authorities

Local governments are essential for ensuring legal and operational viability. Their responsibilities include:

- **Legal and operational:** Recognize informal waste pickers (formally), grant permits, enforce safety standards, and integrate initiatives into municipal systems.
- **Policy and strategy:** Align with national development plans and include informal waste workers through policies, access to waste, and overall social positioning.
- **Infrastructure access:** Enable public-private partnerships and provide access to infrastructure such as landfills or recycling hubs and safe workspaces.
- **Human rights protection:** Avoid criminalizing informal work and ensure social protection and fair treatment.
- **Capacity building and training:** Support training for informal waste pickers to improve health and safety and facilitate the formation of cooperatives.
- **Financial support:** Offer microfinance or revolving funds, incentivize compliance with waste segregation, or provide funding for a specific programme/project to be carried out by a partner (i.e., act as a donor).

Donors

Donors play a pivotal role in financing and innovation, especially considering the long-term sustainability of the programme. Their responsibilities include:

- **Long-term funding:** Move beyond short-term emergency funding and project cycles to support multi-year, integrated waste and livelihood programmes, ensuring funding covers both operational costs and capacity building.
- **Innovation:** Finance pilot projects for new technologies, recycling methods, and circular economy approaches; support research and development for scalable solutions.
- **Cross-sector collaboration:** Promote partnerships (i.e., remove barriers) between actors such as humanitarian actors, waste pickers, the private sector, waste management and environmental organizations, and local governments

Private Sector

Private sector actors are a crucial link in the supply chain towards long-term economic viability and sustainability. Their responsibilities include:

- **Market demand:** Create gateways to purchase sorted recyclables to ensure stable income for waste pickers, develop fair pricing systems (together with other stakeholders), and transparent payment systems.
- **Invest in infrastructure and tools:** Provide pathways for waste pickers to access necessary infrastructure (e.g., machinery, collection points, safe workspaces).
- **Technical expertise:** Offer technical expertise and training, such as training waste pickers on safe handling, quality standards, and business skills.
- **Co-develop innovative business models:** Work together with stakeholders to co-develop scalable business models that integrate informal waste pickers into formalized waste value chains and promote circular economy principles.
- **Ethical and inclusive supply chains:** Promote compliance with human rights and safety standards, including special attention to gender, child labour, and vulnerable groups.

Communities and waste pickers

Last but certainly not least, waste pickers (and the larger community) are key stakeholders in this process. Their responsibilities include:

- **Co-design and plan:** Engage in planning to ensure initiatives reflect local needs, cultural norms, and capacities.
- **Feedback and accountability:** Provide input through participatory monitoring to improve the programme, identify challenges, and propose alternative solutions.
- **Reduce stigma:** Advocate for the inclusion and rights of informal waste pickers and address discrimination to build trust between waste pickers and the larger community.
- **Support local ownership:** Encourage community-led governance structures that foster shared responsibility to maintain a clean and safe environment.

6.4. INTEGRATION WITH LOCAL AND/OR INNOVATIVE WM BUSINESS MODELS

For waste-picking initiatives in humanitarian settings to be sustainable and scalable, they must be embedded within local waste management systems and circular economy business models (Morais et al., 2022). This integration ensures alignment with market dynamics, regulatory frameworks, and long-term development goals while reducing dependency on short-term aid.

To set up a financially sustainable circular economy business model, it is helpful to think about it as a system. The system needs to function from end to end. If one piece is missing, the system will fail. The

system is rarely linear and often requires a combination of various upstream and downstream circular economy business models in combination to function properly (D3.2).

Waste pickers are key actors in efforts to establish circular economy business models in humanitarian contexts. Efforts to do so work best if waste pickers and marginalized groups are integrated from the start; in project design, small and medium-sized enterprises (SME) setup, and market linkage activities. Early engagement builds trust and ensures solutions reflect local realities. Successful humanitarian innovation efforts in this space include efforts to strengthen working conditions for waste pickers through the establishment of formally recognized cooperatives and strengthened financial inclusion.

Innovative models range from cooperatives and micro-enterprises to PPPs, covering activities such as collection, sorting, reuse, repair, and remanufacturing, as previously described. Circular practices—reduce, reuse, recycle—are not new; they have historically emerged from resource scarcity and now underpin formalized systems (Dias, 2016). Expanding these models requires addressing social challenges alongside environmental goals, promoting fair trade recycled materials, and ensuring waste pickers benefit from regenerative strategies (Morais et al., 2022).

Integration offers multiple benefits:

- **Sustainability:** Links programmes to existing value chains and revenue streams.
- **Efficiency:** Leverages local infrastructure and expertise, reducing duplication.
- **Legitimacy:** Builds trust with authorities and communities, supporting policy alignment.
- **Market access:** Connects waste pickers to formal recycling markets and private sector buyers.

Examples of innovation identified during workshops and interviews include plastic-to-products (e.g., buckets, blocks), energy recovery (biodiesel, biogas), organic waste composting or insect-based feed, and reuse of agricultural waste for briquettes. These models demonstrate how humanitarian programmes can catalyze systemic change by combining social inclusion with environmental impact.

Figure 4 depicts an amended circular economy approach to develop a socially restorative model for waste pickers, developed by Barford & Ahmad (2021). It identifies many of the points discussed above, specifically related to the guiding principles. It can also be seen as a foundation to support further research towards the inclusive integration of waste pickers into the circular economy and innovative business models.

Figure 4 Amended circular economy, modified with a reference to waste pickers (Barford & Ahmad, 2021).

7. CONCLUSIONS

Integrating informal waste pickers into humanitarian livelihood programmes is both a social imperative and an environmental opportunity. Waste pickers provide essential services that reduce landfill volumes, prevent pollution, and advance circular economy goals, yet they remain among the most vulnerable workers globally. Humanitarian actors can transform this reality by embedding waste-picking initiatives within broader waste management systems and innovative circular economy business models.

This policy brief underscores that sustainability requires more than short-term interventions. Programmes must prioritize dignity, health, and safety, ensure formal recognition and inclusion, and foster economic empowerment through market linkages and diversification. Co-design with waste pickers and communities is critical to building trust, ownership, and relevance. Partnerships with local authorities, private sector actors, and donors are essential to secure infrastructure, financing, and technical expertise, while advocacy efforts should dismantle stigma and promote social legitimacy.

By adopting these principles, humanitarian programmes can transform waste picking from a precarious survival strategy into a dignified livelihood pathway—one that delivers social protection, economic stability, and environmental benefits. This approach positions waste pickers as key partners in achieving humanitarian objectives and advancing a just, inclusive circular economy.

AI declaration

Co-pilot was used to identify literature (as a complement to a manual literature review), structure text, and provide a language check.

The authors of this deliverable declare that generative AI was only used as a support tool and that the results have been cross-checked, discussed, and interpreted by the authors themselves.

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ANNEX 1

HELP Logistics' waste supply chain mapping tool has been uploaded to the WORM platform on Zenodo / OpenAIRE at <https://zenodo.org/records/17955151>

This annex includes the user guide for the tool.

Supply Chain and Operations Management

Local Waste Value Chain Mapping Methodology for the Humanitarian Sector

June 2024

About Help

Established in 2014, HELP Logistics AG is a non-profit subsidiary of the Kühne Foundation in Switzerland. The organisation operates from logistics hubs strategically located in Amman (Middle East), Dakar (West Africa), Nairobi (East Africa), Hamburg (Germany), and Singapore (Asia-Pacific). HELP Logistics is committed to improving the effectiveness and efficiency of humanitarian supply chains whilst advocating for transformative changes in delivering humanitarian assistance. Our core services encompass supply chain analysis, training, applied research, and outreach. With a dedicated team of 25 experts and collaborating with over 30 organisations from various sectors, we tackle critical challenges in the humanitarian landscape.

The West Africa Office in Dakar, who spearheaded this project, is the youngest office established only in 2019. The office focusses on specific challenges in the West Africa region and in francophone countries and has positioned itself by supporting partner organisations through innovative approaches and by bringing together thought leaders in the region.

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Contents

Contents	3
Abbreviations	4
Figures	5
Tables	6
Preface	7
Collaboration with local waste management stakeholders	8
Waste management organisation in developing countries	9
Waste value chain mapping methodology	12
Stakeholders identification.....	12
Data collection	16
Waste value chain mapping and sector analysis	18
Appendix tables	25
Sources text	29

Abbreviations

ILO	International Labour Organisation
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme

Figures

Figure 1 : Hierarchy of formal waste management framework	9
Figure 2 : Value chain hierarchy of the informal waste management framework.	11
Figure 3 : Most common waste management stakeholders	12
Figure 4 : Indicative list of the most frequent types of waste	15
Figure 5 : Instruction to insert the data collected in the analysis tool	18
Figure 6 : Example of the table mapping of a waste value chain	19
Figure 7 : Example of a waste value chain mapping	20
Figure 8 : Summary of the activities covered by each stakeholder of the waste value chain	21
Figure 9 : Summary of the waste types processed by each group of stakeholders	21
Figure 10 : Various representations of the inflow and outflow characteristics of the waste value chain	21
Figure 11 : Example of insights presented in the socio-demographic analysis section	22
Figure 12 : Examples of visual analysis presented in the business management section	23
Figure 13 : Example of visual analysis of logistics in the waste value chain	24

Tables

Table 1 : List of waste generators	13
Table 2 : List of waste processors	14
Table 3 : Minimum number of interviews	18

Preface

In the face of rising demand for humanitarian assistance, the global solid waste management crisis has become increasingly urgent and underfunded. This crisis disproportionately affects countries that frequently receive humanitarian aid, many of which lack adequate infrastructure and management systems to handle regular solid waste, let alone the additional waste generated by humanitarian efforts.

The substantial waste streams often generated by humanitarian operations mix with existing waste from private and commercial activities in the broader areas of intervention. Despite various initiatives aimed at minimizing waste output from humanitarian operations, the waste generated remains considerable and poses a threat to both current and future generations. Many humanitarian organizations are eager to manage their waste more sustainably but face challenges due to a lack of knowledge about local waste management systems, facilities, and providers.

The methodology presented in this guide comes therefore as a comprehensive framework for understanding and mapping the complex waste management systems in urban and rural areas. Its primary goal is to systematically identify and document all the stakeholders and processes within the waste management chain and create a detailed stakeholder mapping that highlights the flow of waste from generation to final disposal.

This document is designed to be a practical guide for humanitarian organizations aiming to assess the waste systems in their area of activity. It outlines each phase of the methodology applied and includes detailed instructions on how to use the attached Excel template for data organization and analysis.

This methodology is designed to be flexible and adaptable, allowing for modifications based on the context in hand.

Collaboration with local waste management stakeholders

In humanitarian settings, effective waste management is crucial for ensuring environmental sustainability and public health. Integrating waste management into humanitarian interventions not only allows organisations to address immediate health hazards—such as those arising from improperly disposed waste and contaminated water sources—but also contributes to the long-term resilience of the community. It prevents environmental degradation that can lead to further disasters.

By involving local stakeholders of the waste value chain in their waste management initiatives, humanitarian organisations can tap into existing infrastructures and expertise, as local stakeholders usually have good knowledge of the local waste management challenges and opportunities, as well as the cultural practices and existing waste management infrastructure. In parallel to that, collaboration with local waste management actors enhances local capacity development that is vital for long-term maintenance and improvement of waste management practices, while collaboration with local government bodies also ensures local regulatory compliance (UNDP, 2019).

Engaging local waste management actors also helps in strengthening community resilience through income generation and sustainable market development, making it a cornerstone of sustainable humanitarian practice.

Mapping waste management stakeholders and local waste value chains is essential for humanitarian organisations aiming to develop effective waste management plans and reduce the impact of their activities on the operational environment. Detailed maps allow organisations to understand the landscape of local waste management systems, identifying key stakeholders ranging from local government bodies and private companies to informal waste collectors, aggregators, and community groups. By acknowledging each stakeholder's role, linkage and influence, humanitarian organisations can foster effective partnerships to manage the waste generated during and after humanitarian interventions (UNDP, 2019). These partnerships are critical for humanitarian organisations as they enable the implementation of waste management strategies that are culturally appropriate and economically and technically viable.

Furthermore, understanding local waste value chains helps in identifying opportunities to transform waste into resources and divert it from landfills. This not only supports local economies but also reduces environmental impacts by minimising landfilling and open burning at dumpsites, practices often used in developing countries. Through such effective collaboration with local waste management stakeholders, humanitarian organisations can advocate for and implement integrated waste management systems that support circular economy principles. Ultimately, this approach leads to more resilient waste management frameworks that align with both humanitarian goals and local development objectives, ensuring mutual benefits and sustainable practices.

Waste management organisation in developing countries

In developing countries, waste management often presents significant challenges due to limited financial resource and infrastructural deficits (World Bank 2018, UNEP 2024). It is often managed through a collaborative effort between formal and informal actors.

Formal waste management stakeholders are entities officially recognised and regulated by governmental frameworks. They include municipal authorities, private waste management companies, and other organisations that operate under legal and institutional arrangements to provide structured waste collection, transportation, treatment, and disposal services. These stakeholders often work within established guidelines and standards to ensure efficient and environmentally sound waste management practices (ILO 2023, UNEP 2024).

Informal waste management stakeholders, on the other hand, operate outside formal regulatory frameworks and are not officially recognised by government authorities. These include waste pickers, scrap collectors and dealers, and small-scale recyclers (ILO 2023, UNEP 2024) but also more formalised private sector companies working in the waste collection and transformation industry. Informal work involves waste collection and aggregation in general.

National governments are responsible for establishing laws and regulatory frameworks that dictate waste management practices. These frameworks are crucial as they set the standards and guidelines that must be followed to manage waste within their jurisdictions. However, the effectiveness of these frameworks can vary significantly, depending on the capacity and resources of the local governing bodies (World Bank 2018).

Despite the frameworks set by national laws, many local governments in developing countries struggle with the financial and logistical means. Operating such services requires substantial investment in terms of infrastructure, technology, and personnel—all of which entail continuous financial commitments. Due to these constraints, the public waste management services provided are often inefficient and insufficient to meet the needs of the population (World Bank 2018, ILO 2023).

As a result, a substantial portion of waste collection and management is handled by informal actors (ILO 2023). These individuals or small groups operate without official support, filling the gaps left by inadequate formal waste services. They often work under poor conditions and for minimal economic return, yet they play a crucial role in managing waste in areas where formal services are lacking. This informal sector, while crucial, operates without the regulatory safeguards or environmental protections that formal systems might offer, leading to potential public health and environmental risks (ILO 2023). In addition, informal actors only collect economically valuable waste streams, leaving behind no-value waste streams such as soft plastics and much of wet waste such as kitchen waste (UNEP 2023, 2024). As the waste management in developing countries operates with a mixed effort of the formal and informal sectors, it is particularly important to assess stakeholders from both sectors to depict a global vision on how the humanitarian waste can be managed in a responsible and sustainable manner.

Figure 1 : Hierarchy of formal waste management framework

Figure 1 shows the administrative hierarchy of the formal waste management stakeholders, with the National Government representing the highest decision-making power.

Figure 2 : Value chain hierarchy of the informal waste management framework.

Figure 2 shows the value chain hierarchy of informally collected reusable and recyclable materials. The economic value of recovered materials increases with the hierarchy. Waste picking communities are at the bottom of the pyramid with significant social and economic uncertainty, picking reusable and recyclable waste at dumpsites and from the street. Waste collectors usually collect high-value waste such as metals and e-waste, which they sell to middle agents, often called scrap dealers, who trade reusable and recyclable waste streams. Middle agents then sell the scrap to recycling facilities, where recyclable waste is cleaned and reprocessed to ship abroad or to produce recycled products locally.

The methodology presented in this guide for mapping waste value chains mapping presented is structures around three key steps:

Stakeholder Identification: This step involves identifying all relevant actors within the waste value chain, ranging from waste producers to collectors, as well as those who add value through recycling or transformation processes.

Data collection: This phase focuses on gathering data about local waste generation, collection, and disposal practices. It also includes insights into the logistical capacities, characteristics, and challenges faced by stakeholders, as well as opportunities within the sector.

Waste Value Chain Mapping: The final step involves analysing the data collected in the previous phase to understand the flow of waste and interactions among stakeholders. This includes creating visual representations of key indicators, such as the socio-demographic composition of stakeholders, their operational methods, and other critical insights.

Waste value chain mapping methodology

Stakeholders identification

Waste management stakeholders in developing countries can be grouped into three interacting spheres that will be referred to as stakeholder categories, which represent public, non-governmental, and private sectors (Singh, 2015). For clarity purposes, these different categories will be referred to in this report as respectively the “governmental sector”, the “not-for-profit sector” and the “commercial sector”.

The Governmental sector includes national, local, and municipal authorities. Not-for-profit sector includes NGOs, associations, and community-based organisations. The Commercial sector involves waste management companies (collection, transport, disposal), recycling companies, transformative industries, waste pickers and scrap dealers.

A list of the most common stakeholders in each category are identified in **Figure 3**

Figure 3 : Most common waste management stakeholders

The stakeholders identified in **Figure 3** may or may not all be active in the local waste management chain, especially in rural settings. The starting point of this methodology must therefore be a preliminary desk study aimed at contextualizing the waste sector, by identifying the stakeholders that are active in the local waste management chain. This contextual study can be conducted through a review of existing reports from governmental entities, NGOs, academic studies, media articles and other public documents related to the waste management systems (both formal and informal) in the country or, if available, in the specific area of study (city, region, etc.). This desk review will also support the understanding of the regulatory and policy frameworks governing waste management in the country, especially for specialized waste types like hazardous waste, medical waste, or even liquid waste. This framework includes municipal, regional, and national laws that govern waste handling, recycling, and disposal.

In this methodology, stakeholders within the waste value chain are categorized into two distinct groups: **waste generators** and **waste processors**. Waste generators refer to entities that produce waste, whereas waste processors encompass those responsible for the collection, recycling, transformation, or disposal of the waste produced. This classification helps streamline the mapping of waste flows by clearly delineating the sources of waste from the entities involved in its management and processing.

Table 1 : List of waste generators

Stakeholder Group	Stakeholder type	Definition
Waste Generator	Households and Residential Complexes	Includes individual homes, apartments, and condominiums.
Waste Generator	Commercial and Administrative Facilities	Covers offices, retail stores, restaurants, hotels, and other business-related establishments.
Waste Generator	Industrial and Construction Sites	Encompasses factories, warehouses, construction sites, and manufacturing plants.
Waste Generator	Public and Recreational Spaces	Includes parks, streets, sports arenas, and entertainment venues.
Waste Generator	Institutional and Service Providers	Covers educational institutions, utilities, and transportation hubs.
Waste Generator	Health Facilities	Includes hospitals, clinics, pharmacies, etc.

Table 2 : List of waste processors

Stakeholder Group	Stakeholder type	Definition
Waste Processor	National Government / State sanitation services	These are central government bodies responsible for creating and enforcing regulations related to waste management. They develop national policies, standards, and frameworks to ensure effective waste management practices across the country.
Waste Processor	Municipal authorities / Local sanitation services	These are local government entities tasked with the management of waste at the municipal level. Their responsibilities typically include organizing waste collection, transportation, and disposal services within their jurisdiction, as well as maintaining sanitation infrastructure.
Waste Processor	Community based waste management associations	These are organizations formed by local communities to address waste management issues at a grassroots level. They often play a role in waste collection, sorting, and recycling, especially in areas where formal waste management services are limited.
Waste Processor	Waste pickers	Individuals who collect and sort through waste materials, often informally, to retrieve items that can be recycled or sold. They play a crucial role in waste recovery, especially in regions with limited formal recycling systems.
Waste Processor	Waste collectors	These are entities or individuals responsible for the collection of waste from households, businesses, and other sources. They transport the waste to designated facilities for processing, recycling, or disposal.

Waste Processor	Scrap dealers	Businesses or individuals who buy, sell, and trade recyclable materials, such as metals, plastics, and paper. They act as intermediaries in the recycling value chain by purchasing materials from waste pickers and collectors and selling them to recycling facilities.
Waste Processor	Public recycling and final disposal facilities	Government-owned facilities that process recyclable materials and manage the final disposal of non-recyclable waste. These facilities ensure that waste is treated in an environmentally responsible manner.
Waste Processor	Private recycling companies	Privately owned enterprises that specialize in the processing of recyclable materials. They transform waste into reusable raw materials or products and contribute to the circular economy by diverting waste from landfills.
Waste Processor	Manufacturing / Transformation industries	Companies that use recycled or processed waste materials as inputs to manufacture new products. These industries are vital for creating value from waste, as they close the loop by integrating recycled materials into production processes.

In parallel to the stakeholders identification, this preliminary study must also support in confirming the different types of waste that are generated and processed in the area of study. The methodology presented in this guide is based on the following list of the most frequent waste types found in literature. This list can however be complemented with all other additional waste types that may be found in the desk study.

Figure 4 : Indicative list of the most frequent types of waste

Data collection

The purpose of this step is to collect detailed information that will help identify the connections and interactions between the different stakeholders in the waste chain and understand the flows of waste within the system. This is achieved by having each stakeholder respond to a series of questions about the type of waste they generate or collect, the sources from which they collect it, and their methods of disposal or the subsequent stakeholders to whom they pass on the waste. The inputs thus obtained will be used in a subsequent step to map out the entire waste value chain and create a directory of local waste stakeholders, providing detailed information on each respondent's role in the waste chain and the types of waste they manage. Additionally, the data collected will allow to delve deeper into each stakeholder's capacity, business practices, logistical operations, and the challenges and opportunities they perceive within the sector. This provides a holistic view of the local waste management landscape and provides humanitarian partners with practical insights on how they can support and enhance the waste sector in their areas of intervention.

Enumerators training

The data collection can be carried out by one or more enumerators, depending on the size of the area to be covered. It is recommended to select enumerators who are familiar with local waste management practices and have a strong knowledge of the area. This familiarity will enable them to navigate various locations efficiently and engage effectively with the different stakeholders. Additionally, selected enumerators should have experience in conducting surveys using digital tools, such as Kobo Toolbox, to ensure accurate and efficient data collection.

Before the start of their mission, the selected enumerators must be briefed on the context and objectives of the survey and trained on the use of the data collection questionnaire. It is recommended to allocate two days for training the enumerators and field-testing the questionnaire.

The initial phase of the training can be conducted in a traditional classroom setting, in person or online if the network quality allows. The first day of the enumerators training should focus on:

- Providing a brief overview of the **main findings and conclusions** from the preliminary contextual study to give enumerators an understanding of local waste management practices.
- Outlining the overall goal of the waste value chain mapping exercise, specifically the **objectives of the data collection mission** and the anticipated impact of their work.
- Going through the **questionnaire in detail**, explaining the purpose of each question. This is especially crucial if the assessment is conducted in a language different from that of the questionnaire, to ensure clarity and prevent misinterpretation. This should include demonstrations on navigating various question types (e.g., multiple choice, open-ended, and numeric).
- Training the enumerators on essential points to consider such as making the respondents feel comfortable sharing information, obtaining informed consent from respondents, ensuring confidentiality of their responses, and handling sensitive information professionally.

The second day of training should be dedicated to:

- Ensuring the data collection tool is properly installed on all devices to be used in the field.
- Deploying the questionnaire on the field to test and make necessary adjustments to the data collection tool, if needed. Conducting a live trial of the survey will also allow to assess its effectiveness and ensure the integrity of the data collected, with corrections made before the actual fieldwork begins.

Field mission

The data collection survey must be conducted using the questionnaire presented in the Appendix tables. This questionnaire is preferably deployed using Kobo Toolbox but can be adapted to fit in any other data collection tool.

The data collection must start from an entry point to the waste value chain that would typically be a waste generating stakeholder. This could be a refugee camp, a private organisation or an NGO, a household, a beneficiary distribution site, etc. depending on the context of the study.

The formal waste management stakeholders (government related actors) are best assessed « top-down » in the order of hierarchy presented in **Figure 1**. By conducting interviews from the top of the pyramid, it is possible to identify the stakeholders and actors in the subsequent hierarchy level. The assessment can involve the following steps:

- Identify the municipal service responsible for waste management and interview them using the field assessment questionnaire.
- If waste management services are outsourced to private companies, ask municipal authorities and/or conduct online research to identify the private-sector waste management and hazardous waste management companies that they contract to and interview them using the same questionnaire.

The informal waste management stakeholders are best assessed « bottom-up » in the order of hierarchy presented in **Figure 2** as it might be easier to find waste pickers in areas of humanitarian intervention. The assessment can involve the following steps:

- Meet with waste picking communities in a landfill site, commercial area, and/or on the streets. Interview them using the field assessment questionnaire. Each waste picker interviewed must be asked to provide the contact of at least one scrap dealer for each type of waste they collect.
- Contact the scrap dealers identified from the waste pickers interviews and survey them using the same questionnaire. Each scrap dealer interviewed must be asked to provide the contact of the recyclers they sell their waste to or the waste pickers and collectors they buy waste from. Each recyclable waste type identified during the interviews with the scrap dealers should have an end-user (recycler).
- Contact the recyclers indicated by the scrap dealers and interview them using the same questionnaire.
- Following this logic, each additional stakeholder identified in the interviews must also be surveyed to lead to the next or the previous node in the waste value chain.

A minimum number of interviews to conduct with each type of stakeholders are recommended in Table 3. These numbers are derived from the results of the methodology pilot and represent the minimum necessary to achieve a

meaningful mapping of the waste value chain. The analytical tool that will be used in the next step of this methodology to process the data collected can however process up to 260 entries.

Table 3 : Minimum number of interviews

Waste stakeholder type	Minimum number of respondents recommended
Waste generator	2
Waste pickers	20
Middle agents/ scrap dealers	10
Recycling companies	2
National waste management company	1
Community based associations	2

Waste value chain mapping and sector analysis

After all the interviews are completed, the data collected must be exported from the chosen data collection tool into a Microsoft Excel file for the data analysis phase. The analysis must be conducted using a specific data analysis workbook. This data analysis tool is compatible with Microsoft Excel and must be ran using a **macro-enabled version**.

The worktables can be requested at: help.senegal@kuehne-foundation.org

The steps to follow to update the analysis and the dashboards are presented in the Worksheet named **“Guide”**, as presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5 : Instruction to insert the data collected in the analysis tool

The analysis of the data collected allows to create a visual representation of the waste value chain, including the stakeholders and the waste flows. Additionally, it also provides insights into the local waste management sector, especially regarding the socio-demographic characteristics of the stakeholders involved, as well as their business management practices and the logistical operations.

Value chain mapping

This section presents the table mapping of the local waste value chain, which is an aggregation of all the information collected from the different stakeholders of the waste value chain regarding their inflows and outflows. It presents the different waste streams going from one stakeholder to another in the waste value chain. This table mapping can be used to create a visual representation of the waste flows, using any data visualization or mapping tool. The example below was obtained using Miro.

Figure 6 : Example of the table mapping of a waste value chain

From	To
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▣ Commercial and Administrative Facilities 	National Government / State sanitation services
	Waste collectors
	Private recycling companies
	Waste pickers
	Scrap dealers
	Municipal authorities / Local sanitation services
	Manufacturing / Transformation industries
	Community based waste management associations
	Public recycling and final disposal facilities
	Municipal authorities / Local sanitation services
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▣ Community based waste management associations 	National Government / State sanitation services
	Waste collectors
	Municipal authorities / Local sanitation services
	Manufacturing / Transformation industries
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▣ Health Facilities 	National Government / State sanitation services
	Waste collectors
	Municipal authorities / Local sanitation services
	Manufacturing / Transformation industries
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▣ Health facility 	Community based waste management associations
	Public recycling and final disposal facilities
	Waste collectors
	Municipal authorities / Local sanitation services
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▣ Households and Residential Complexes 	Waste collectors
	Waste pickers
	Municipal authorities / Local sanitation services
	Manufacturing / Transformation industries
	Community based waste management associations
	Public recycling and final disposal facilities
	National Government / State sanitation services
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▣ Industrial and Construction Sites 	Waste collectors
	Scrap dealers
	Municipal authorities / Local sanitation services
	Manufacturing / Transformation industries
	Community based waste management associations
	Public recycling and final disposal facilities
	National Government / State sanitation services

Figure 7 : Example of a waste value chain mapping

This visual mapping of the local waste value chain, illustrating the different stakeholders and their interactions, can help humanitarian organisations understand how to effectively process their waste within their areas of intervention. Understanding the complexity of the waste value chain allows them to anticipate and plan their waste management strategies more effectively. In areas with a more intricate and interconnected waste chain, humanitarian organisations can predict potential challenges and identify opportunities for collaboration with and support to local waste management stakeholders. Conversely, in regions where the waste value chain is less developed, organisations might need to invest more in capacity-building and infrastructure development to ensure sustainable waste management.

The complementary tables, which summarize the various stakeholders and the types of waste they each collect and process, provides a clear overview of which waste types are well-managed and recycled in the area of study, and which are not. Humanitarian organisations can use this information to ensure their waste management practices are sustainable by minimising their production of the waste types that are not adequately managed by the local actors of the waste chain. If avoiding such waste is not feasible, humanitarian organisations could consider engaging with local stakeholders, as part of their intervention, to explore ways to support the development of proper processing capabilities. This could involve providing technical assistance, facilitating partnerships, or advocating for improved infrastructure.

Figure 8 : Summary of the activities covered by each stakeholder of the waste value chain

Activities covered by each group of stakeholder				
Stakeholder Type	Waste collection	Waste selling	Waste transformation	Waste recycling / reuse
National Government / State sanitation services	Regularly	Never	Regularly	Regularly
Municipal authorities / Local sanitation services	Regularly	Never	Regularly	Often
Community based waste management associations	Never	Regularly	Never	Never
Waste pickers	Regularly	Regularly	Rarely	Rarely
Waste collectors	Regularly	Regularly	Rarely	Rarely
Scrap dealers	Often	Regularly	Often	Sometimes
Public recycling and final disposal facilities	Never	Regularly	Regularly	Never
Private recycling companies	Never	Regularly	Regularly	Regularly
Manufacturing / Transformation industries	Never	Regularly	Often	Regularly

Figure 9 : Summary of the waste types processed by each group of stakeholders

Type of waste that are collected or processed by each group of stakeholder															
Stakeholder Type	Hard Plastics	Food waste	Fleet waste	metal alloys (steel, stainless steel, brass, bronze)	Other	Non-ferrous metals (copper, aluminium, lead, nickel, tin)	Ferrous metals (iron, steel, cast iron)	Soft plastics	E-waste	Liquid waste (sewage, wastewater, stormwater, drainage water)	Hazardous waste	Medical waste	PET Bottles	Paper and cardboard	Glass Containers
National Government / State sanitation services	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Regularly	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never
Municipal authorities / Local sanitation services	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Regularly	Never	Rarely	Rarely	Never	Never	Never
Community based waste management associations	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Regularly	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never
Waste pickers	Rarely	Sometimes	Never	Regularly	Often	Regularly	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	Never	Never	Never	Rarely	Never	Rarely
Waste collectors	Often	Rarely	Rarely	Often	Rarely	Often	Often	Rarely	Never	Never	Never	Never	Often	Rarely	Sometimes
Scrap dealers	Rarely	Rarely	Never	Never	Sometimes	Never	Often	Rarely	Regularly	Never	Never	Never	Rarely	Rarely	Rarely
Public recycling and final disposal facilities	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Regularly	Never	Regularly	Never	Never	Never	Never
Private recycling companies	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Regularly	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never
Manufacturing / Transformation industries	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Regularly	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never	Never

Figure 10 : Various representations of the inflow and outflow characteristics of the waste value chain

Furthermore, the directory of local actors obtained through the field assessment interviews enable humanitarian organisations to identify relevant stakeholders they can collaborate with for sustainable and locally acceptable waste management practices. By leveraging these connections, humanitarian organisations can enhance their waste management strategies, contributing to both environmental sustainability and community development. This approach not only helps in reducing the environmental impact of their operations but also empowers local communities and fosters economic growth through more efficient and effective waste management practices.

Socio demographic analysis

The socio-demographic analysis enables organizations to gain a comprehensive understanding of the stakeholders involved in the waste value chain. This includes insights into their gender, age, education, and experience, as well as their motivations for working in the waste sector. Additionally, the analysis provides valuable information about their income levels, challenges they face, and the types of support they may need to enhance their operations and overall well-being. By understanding these factors, organizations can develop targeted strategies to better support stakeholders and improve the effectiveness of waste management initiatives.

Figure 11 : Example of insights presented in the socio-demographic analysis section

Business management

The business management section examines how both formal and informal stakeholders operate within the waste value chain. This includes an analysis of their collaborative efforts, their level of knowledge regarding waste processing, and their overall training. Additionally, the analysis presents an assessment of their capacities to manage operations effectively, providing a comprehensive understanding of how these stakeholders contribute to the waste management ecosystem.

Figure 12 : Examples of visual analysis presented in the business management section

Logistics

In the logistics section, the management of logistical flows of waste by stakeholders is examined, focusing on aspects such as storage, transportation, planning and costs. Additionally, logistics challenges faced by stakeholders are investigated, providing insights into the efficiency and effectiveness of their operations. This analysis helps to identify areas for improvement and potential support in optimizing logistics strategies in the waste value chain.

Figure 13 : Example of visual analysis of logistics in the waste value chain

In conclusion, the waste value chain mapping methodology presented in this guide provides a comprehensive framework for humanitarian organisations to understand the local waste management flows, capacities, and stakeholders in their areas of intervention and improve their waste management processes. By identifying gaps and opportunities within the local waste management ecosystem, organisations can implement targeted interventions that support sustainable development goals and promote a circular economy. This proactive approach, informed by the complexity of the local waste value chains, ensures that organisations can manage their waste more efficiently and sustainably, ultimately benefiting both the environment and the local communities.

Appendix tables

Appendix 1 : Data collection questionnaire

WASTE VALUE CHAIN MAPPING SURVEY

Informations sur le téléphone

Start time: 2024-10-24T11:45:40.484-00:00

Date: 2024-10-24

S1. General informations

S1.1. Stakeholder name

S1.2. Stakeholder group

- Waste Generator
- Waste Processor

S1.3. Stakeholder type

S1.4. Type of activity

- Waste collection - recycling - reselling
- Local Food and Drink Makers (e.g., Juice Sellers, Street Vendors)
- Mechanical Repair Shops
- Electronic Repair Technicians
- Small-Scale Craft Makers
- Agriculture and Horticulture Entrepreneur
- Eco-artists
- Construction and Building Material Suppliers

S1.5. Contact information (Telephone)

S1.6. Age (years)

S1.7. Gender

- Male
- Female

S1.8. Academic level

- Primary School
- Middle School
- High School
- No education
- Arabic education
- College / University

S1.9. How Long have you been working in the waste sector ?

S1.10. How many collaborators do you have (0 if you work alone)?

S1.11. Who do you collaborate with ?

- Work Alone
- Collaborate with Family
- Collaborate with business partners

S1.12. Do you work in a formally registered business or do you operate informally?

- Informal business
- Formal business

S1.13. How many people are in the household you belong to (household of spouse and dependents living in the same location)

S1.14. How many people in the household (including you) work in the waste value chains?

S1.15. How many of them are children (aged under 15) ?

S1.16. Is your waste related activity your main source of income ?

- Yes
- No

S1.17. If not, what is your main source of income ?

- Street vending or small-scale trading (clothes, food items)
- Domestic work (cleaning, childcare)
- Transport and delivery (taxi, bus, train, motorcycle, etc.)
- Handyman services (plumbing, electrical)
- Craftsmanship (making and selling crafts)
- Manufacturing or factory work
- Tailoring and Hairdressing
- Repair services (electronics, cars, etc.)
- Artist or artisan
- Office job (administrative, clerical)
- Agriculture
- Fishing
- Teaching or tutoring
- Healthcare services (nurse, community health worker)
- Retail (working in shops or stores)
- Construction (skilled labor, masonry)
- Hospitality (hotel, restaurant staff)
- Security services (guard, watchman)
- Other

S1.18. What is your average monthly revenue earned from waste related activities ?

S1.19. What is your average monthly revenue earned from your other sources of income ?

S1.20. Are you the main provider of your household ?

- Yes
- No

S1.21. What are the main challenges encountered in your activity ?

- Safety issues
- Social stigma
- Low level of revenues
- Transport capacity
- Access to markets
- Storage capacity
- Losses and Theft
- Health issues
- Unsufficient training and knowledge
- Risk exposure

S1.22. What do you do with your inflows ?

- Sell locally
- Reuse
- Recycle
- Sell for export
- Transform
- Landfill
- Composting

S1.23. What is the main output of your activity (what do you produce) ?

- No processing
- Animal feed
- Compost
- Spare parts
- Transformed product

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**Waste in humanitarian Operations:
Reduction and Minimisation**

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